

Building Self-Sustaining Research and Innovation Ecosystems in Europe through
Responsible Research and Innovation

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Description of the deliverable	As main outcome of Task 4.2 this report presents the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework, whose purpose is to help policy-makers and practitioners in developing RRI-enabled, self-sustaining R&I ecosystems addressing main societal challenges. The Framework is built on state-of-the-art systems and complexity thinking, profiting from a wide domain of concepts, presented here as the SeeRRI Thesaurus. Both the Framework and the Thesaurus are applicable to SeeRRI itself and beyond.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the outcomes of SeeRRI Task 4.2 "Framework for a self-sustaining ecosystem", whose objective is to produce a Conceptual Framework to be used in SeeRRI itself and in other initiatives in the future. The purpose of this framework is to help policy-makers and practitioners in the system-wide deployment of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in territorial contexts. SeeRRI adopts a reading of RRI beyond the adaptation of R&I processes to new formal requirements: it intends to **leverage RRI as an instrument of transformation of R&I activities to make them both self-sustaining and capable of addressing the main societal challenges**. The report includes an analysis of the current framing of R&I processes, initially established and deployed in the USA after the end of World War II, and how it has not been able to address undesirable consequences of R&I activities and outcomes. These consequences are now first-order threats to the future of humanity, including growing social inequalities, climate warming, the dramatic loss of biodiversity and the exhaustion of non-renewable resources, among others. As shown by the Covid-19 pandemic, our highly technological societies are more fragile and exposed than we thought to unexpected consequences of our actions, even coming from the most primitive of biological materials.

The SeeRRI Conceptual Framework uses a systemic perspective and state-of-the-art thinking from process philosophy, complexity theory, cybernetics and ecology, among other disciplines. Recognizing that reality is the outcome of countless ongoing processes enables a systemic approach focused on dynamic evolution rather than on static structures. This exercise builds upon established frameworks of RRI (operational and process dimensions), the EU Regional Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization (RIS3) and the work done and results obtained in SeeRRI WP2, WP3, Task 4.1 of WP4, WP5 and WP6. SeeRRI develops its Conceptual Framework taking into account **complexity as a fundamental characteristic of our societies, challenges and goals**. All of these are dependent on the multiplicity of contexts, actors and interactions involved in R&I activities, whose evolution in a deliberate direction requires new conceptual tools. The main question addressed here is **how policy-makers and practitioners can foster in a practical way transformations of R&I ecosystems in the desired direction, without denying or betraying the complexity of the intent**.

In response to that question, two elements are central:

- A **shift of worldview towards complexity thinking** is required, both to have a better understanding of the most pressing challenges of humanity and to facilitate the task of policy-makers and practitioners in the kind of transformations envisioned;
- Transformations are **processes of mutual learning** among territorial actors working together to create the conditions for the R&I ecosystems to develop new patterns of relevance to address our existential challenges.

This report has two complementary parts:

- **Sections 1 and 2** present the rationale and describe the fundamental assumptions of the Conceptual Framework, starting with Assumption Zero (adopting a process-oriented lens) and following with **Communities, Ecosystems, Interdependencies, Transformations, Wellbeing(s) in Biosphere and Mutual Learning**. **Section 3** describes the integrated use of the Conceptual Framework in SeeRRI and the different elements deriving from it: **Set of Questions, Mutual Learning Process, Shared Agendas, formulation of territorial challenges, and trigger processes**.

- **Section 4** is a Thesaurus, i.e. a repository of 34 concepts or conceptual areas whose individual descriptions can be useful to the reader in a multiplicity of contexts. More elaborated versions are presented **in an Annex**. The explanation of concepts integrates academic knowledge from different disciplines as well as elements of conversations among SeeRRI partners and territorial stakeholders in workshops and meetings during the first 15 months of activity of the project. The Conceptual Framework is the current endpoint of a journey which has been collectively travelled during that period, not necessarily in a linear way. Our roadmap is represented here (**see figure 1**) and integrated in the report through the six parts in which the Thesaurus of 34 concepts is divided.

Figure 1. The spiral roadmap leading to SeeRRI Conceptual Framework (source: own elaboration)

The report closes with a brief **Postface**, reflecting on the context of Covid-19 and its consequences, from a systemic perspective.

1. RATIONALE FOR THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

1.1. THE DAUNTING TASK OF POLICY-MAKERS

Nowadays the world is full of confusing signals. Humanity seems to be thriving and committing suicide at the same time. For sure, many elements of judgment are positive. Life expectancy has been steadily increasing. Literacy is slowly but surely reaching the entire humanity. Not without obstacles and setbacks, women are emancipating everywhere. For a large part of humanity aspirations to better levels of wellbeing are getting closer to realization. Science and technology are breaking barriers in our knowledge and capacity to act. To many, caring for one another is the meaning of life. At the same time, social inequalities are widening fast, political polarization and geopolitical risks are increasing, and technological innovation is also creating the possibility of dystopian futures with deeper divisions between winners and losers. Human-induced climate change and other effects of industrialization are destroying the natural foundations on which human life depends. Exhaustion of workable fossil fuels is closing an era of accessible energy with high returns. On top of all that, the impacts of Covid-19 are showing the fragility and systemic complexity of our highly technological societies: a health emergency provoked by a primitive piece of biological material is able to destabilize our whole economies, with deep social and possibly political consequences.

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) addresses these complex realities, and SwafS-14 combines RRI with a territorial perspective. Stating "*the **complexity of the challenges** set by the interplay between science and society*", the topic description invokes the advantage of local actors to address "*the status quo of the **complex relationships** between cultural, social, economic and political actors, of the local dynamics, history, expectations and requirements as well as specific concerns*". In response to the challenges, "*the RRI approach (...) aims to encourage societal actors to work together during the whole research and innovation (R&I) process to better align R&I and its outcomes with the **values, needs and expectations of society***". And "*territories can work towards the establishment of **self-sustaining R&I ecosystems** that are characterized by a high degree of openness, democratic accountability, and responsiveness to need by taking action to promote all parts of RRI*" [EC 2019] (all emphases are ours).

In the context so defined, policy-makers, practitioners and stakeholders alike face a daunting task, that of **combining three major goals** at the same time:

- promoting the deployment of RRI in all its dimensions;
- ensure that territorial R&I ecosystems are self-sustaining, and
- make R&I activities work to effectively address the societal challenges of our times.

The Regional Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization (RIS3) offers a framework for the process of policy making, implementation and governance for public support to R&I in territorial contexts. It is represented in **figure 2**. A straightforward response to the task defined above is to combine RIS3 with RRI and the Agenda 2030 of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [UN 2015]. The Agenda 2030 is officially supported by the European Union and its Member States, and it is the most comprehensive response to the confusing situation and challenges of humanity described above. It was established at a global level but its provisions are equally valid at all scales of policy-making and governance.

In practical terms, if one follows the philosophy of RRI (reflect, include, respond, anticipate) and takes into account the complex nature of society, all the stages represented in **figure 2** are problematic:

- Is there only one context to analyze? Health, nature, economy, politics, science, technology, culture, society are all intertwined (as shown in the Covid-19 crisis), so the boundary of the area of analysis is difficult to discern, and additionally the analysis may provide contradictory conclusions;

Figure 2. The multi-stage framing of RIS3 (source: Online S3 platform)

- Formulating an appropriate strategy is a challenge in itself since our purpose is to transform R&I ecosystems so that they align with societal values, expectations and needs. Both elements of this alignment exercise are complex systems and moving targets;
- Priority setting could reveal a nightmare of entangled trade-offs: the inclusion of all kinds of stakeholders and perspectives creates a multiplicity of goals and makes frequently appear diverging interests. Economic growth used to be the priority "par excellence", but now (and for good reasons) it is only 1 of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs);
- Policies to be implemented are also multiple and intersecting: RIS3, RRI and the Agenda 2030 can lead to contradictory injunctions, not to talk about other ongoing policies;
- Monitoring and evaluation, if performed in the conventional way, is an increasingly difficult task since it has to be multi-dimensional: e.g. the Agenda 2030 has 232 indicators. How is it possible to ensure that progress is being made when reality is so complex?
- And the governance of the whole cycle is not the smallest of the challenges in times of social fragmentation, political polarization, "fake news" and declining trust in the existing institutions.

The combination of RRI, RIS3 and the Agenda 2030 is an ambitious endeavour setting the course for deep transformations in the dynamic of territorial R&I ecosystems and in the public support they receive. In this context the above framing of RIS3 is not sufficient to provide effective guidance to policy-makers and practitioners. The role of SeeRRI is to provide a set of additional elements to address that insufficiency from a perspective consistent with:

- the complex nature of what policy-makers intend to achieve,
- the best understanding of how complex systems change,
- the potential of RRI as enabler of societal transformations.

1.2. THE SEERRI APPROACH

SeeRRI is built upon the development of three initial ideas:

- to achieve the goals described in 1.1, changes are required in the dynamics of whole R&I ecosystems: changes at the level of individual organizations involved in R&I are not sufficient;
- the best of knowledge is needed on complexity, ecosystems and paradigm shifts;
- changes in complex systems do not happen through a conventional approach of setting goals, defining a roadmap and establishing sets of indicators.

SeeRRI makes use of concepts grounded in decades of research in systems thinking about what "complexity" means and how "ecosystems" work. This is the intellectual driver of the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework described in this report, as main outcome of Task 4.2 (Framework for self-sustaining R&I ecosystems) in WP4 (Development and Validation of an Integrated Framework). The development of the framework is a process also fed by the analyses of the territories done in WP2 (Active Mapping of SeeRRI Territorial R&I Ecosystems), the discussions with the Consortium partners and the territorial stakeholders engaged in WP3 (Stakeholder Engagement) and WP5 (Implementing Actions), and the work done in WP6 (Impact Assessment and Activities Evaluation).

The SeeRRI Conceptual Framework enables the collective capacity to ask better questions and initiate pathways to new patterns: it is not a top-down blueprint to be applied as a recipe to get from present A to future B as if it was valid for all contexts. On one hand the SeeRRI approach integrates the fact that complex systems do not obey external injunctions and do not evolve linearly along a planned roadmap [Meadows 2002]. SeeRRI brings to RRI the recognition that its transformative role, in both R&I processes and societal challenges, is better achieved through the ignition of processes of mutual learning involving all actors and a variety of cultural perspectives (see 2.3). To that end, asking better questions is a requirement and the Conceptual Framework is a question machine (see 3.2). This is consistent with how the RRI concept itself was conceived, by questioning science, innovation and technology and unveiling our blind spots about the processes through which we acquire and develop new knowledge, and how these are framed (see 4.1).

This reflection mirrors the historical evolution of scientific paradigms [Kuhn 1962], the realization that we have entered an era of "post-normal science" [Funtowicz & Ravetz 1993] and the emergence of complexity thinking [Abraham 2002]. This is not only an academic discussion of interest to philosophers of science. In the last three centuries more than ever before, research and innovation have been extremely effective tools to transform the world around us and create the conditions for what we consider as "wellbeing". That transformative success calls for continuing the adventure of R&I

towards further progress. However, we have started realizing that progress came at a huge cost. Among many other factors, an excessive increase in the average atmospheric temperature will make human life on Earth impossible, unless we take dramatic steps. This cannot be labelled as a "collateral" effect. In a different worldview we could interpret the climate emergency as a gigantic feedback loop by the self-regulating Earth system. Reframing climate warming in that way is a good exercise to expose some of our blind spots and paradoxes: the most highly valued human capacities of science and technology are leading to the fragility and possible collapse of human civilizations, as anticipated 50 years ago by the Club of Rome [Meadows et al 1972].

The first manifestations of our self-inflicted course towards collapse have coincided with the questioning of the dominant mechanistic worldview (see 4.2). This is more than a coincidence: it is an invitation to consider other epistemologies (see 4.1.2 and 4.5) as a means to overcome the blindness of mechanistic frameworks to interdependencies and hence to most of the consequences of our actions. We know now that a big gap exists between the way we have been thinking and the way nature works. Not bridging that gap is extremely irresponsible. This opening to new worldviews also enables us to view the RRI-driven process of reframing and transformation of R&I ecosystems in a non-mechanistic way. By defining it as a process of mutual learning, it invites **all territorial stakeholders to collaborate in co-creating the conditions for the R&I ecosystems to develop new patterns of relevance to address our existential challenges.**

Figure 3. Relationships between RIS3 and SeeRRI Thesaurus (source: own elaboration)

In other words, the change of epistemology we need to have a better understanding of the most pressing challenges of humanity is the same required to facilitate the daunting task for policy-makers that has been described in 1.1. The SeeRRI Conceptual Framework is the materialization of that epistemological shift for the purposes of the project. Figure 3 maps the relationships between the stages of RIS3 and the many concepts and areas of knowledge inspiring the Conceptual Framework. This map complements the 6-stage framing of RIS3 and paves the way to **a substantially different way of doing, more consistent with the complexity of both the challenges and the task of combining RIS3, RRI and the Agenda 2030**. Numbers indicated in figure 3 refer to the entries in the Thesaurus (Section 4), where the concepts and knowledge areas are presented. More detailed explanations about each of them can be found in the Annex to this report.

To be clear, we are not suggesting to overload the agenda of policy-makers, practitioners and stakeholders with the task of mastering all the concepts shown, coming from so many scientific disciplines. Those concepts are the hidden part of the iceberg and need not be mastered by users of frameworks built upon them. They ensure the consistency with the state-of-the-art in systems and complexity thinking. The SeeRRI Conceptual Framework, as described in Sections 2 and 3, is the practical result to be used by whoever shares the purposes here exposed.

1.3. THE GENDER DIMENSION OF THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In terms of gender balance systems thinking is an unfortunately rare but positive case in the history of science. Contributions to the field by women have been significant from the very beginning and largely shaped the evolution of knowledge and agendas of research. Ada Lovelace, at the onset in the 1830s of what later became computer science, is a case in point. In the 20th century and more recent times, coming from many different backgrounds Donella Meadows, Margaret Mead, Mary Catherine and Nora Bateson, Elinor Ostrom, Isabelle Stengers, Olivia Bina, Rika Preiser, Maja Göpel, Mariana Mazzucato, Petra Künkel, Lene Rachel Andersen, Nicole Dewandre, Anne Snick, among many others, have produced relevant contributions to the large domain of systems thinking and complexity theory, making an immense impact inside and outside the boxes of their specific fields of knowledge.

Moreover, the assumptions of the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework integrate views balancing reductionistic and holistic arguments, in a way taking into consideration alternative perspectives. This echoes the process by which women have been able to become recognized in public spheres of deliberation. It is for instance noticeable that the process of shifting to the “wellbeing economy” (from which the SeeRRI assumption of Wellbeing(s) in Biosphere takes part of its inspiration) is largely led by women political leaders all around the world, e.g. in New Zealand (Prime Minister Jacinda Ardern), Iceland (Prime Minister Katrín Jakobsdóttir) and Scotland (First Minister Nicola Sturgeon). We take for granted this is not a coincidence: both the progress of systems thinking as a discipline and its impact in society are made possible by a stronger role of women in research and action. Taking into account all these circumstances we expect the Conceptual Framework of SeeRRI to resonate strongly with audiences working for a prominent role of women in leading the paradigm shift towards RRI and sustainable wellbeing.

2. SEERRI CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

We present here the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework through the explicit statement of 1+6 assumptions that we assume of value for the purposes the project pursues. This is an untypical but deliberate way of elaborating a framework. The form is here in accordance with the substance. Since the recognition of the systemic nature of reality (with ourselves inside) is at the core of our approach, it would not have made sense to present a detailed blueprint for the engineered construction of RRI-inspired self-sustaining R&I ecosystems in whatever number of straightforward steps. We know that in absence of a step-by-step blueprint, the interpretation and use of SeeRRI Conceptual Framework requires the active involvement of actors in processes of mutual learning necessarily context-dependent and unpredictable to an extent. But this is what is consistent with the philosophical and methodological foundations of our approach, in our best attempt to avoid the excess of conscious purpose and to become victims of our blind spots (see 4.1.4 and 4.1.5). Section 3 describes with some detail the integrated use of the Conceptual Framework in SeeRRI and potentially beyond.

2.1. ASSUMPTION ZERO

Assumption Zero is “process philosophy” (see 4.2.4), i.e. the hypothesis that reality is the outcome of a multitude of autonomous processes unfolding in parallel over time in places, scales, and contexts, and producing structures in permanent evolution and interaction. Structures are not previous to processes, they are configurations reflecting the state of play of processes at a certain moment. These are permanently exchanging energy, resources and information with their environment, created by other processes. According to this description, there is nothing in reality which could be purely static and the persistence of processes depends on their adaptation to context. They can be contradictory with each other and all of them are engaged in the pursuit of persistence. Among different ways of adopting a systemic perspective, this one gives prominence to interdependencies (see 2.2.5 and 4.5.2) and to the dynamic character of any system, natural or human.

In this perspective, the analysis of the capacity of processes to persist is most relevant. In the context of SeeRRI it is critical to investigate how RRI-inspired processes of research and innovation can be successful in comparison with more conventional ones, as far as the dynamic of deployment of RRI is concerned. Regarding which criteria could be used to analyze the persistence of processes, and with it the possibility of self-organization (see 4.5.3), we consider the following (see 4.6.5):

- Openness: processes have to be able to exchange with their environment in order to evolve and adapt while keeping their own identity and singularity;
- Energy: processes are embodied in far-from-equilibrium dynamic entities which need to capture energy from their environment;
- Auto-catalysis: to keep the processes alive and thriving, their outcomes have to reinforce the processes themselves.

In practical terms these criteria can be translated into concrete questions regarding the processes underlying regional R&I ecosystems, especially on how transformations towards RRI can overcome obstacles (as detailed in Section 3).

2.2. BUILDING UPON CONCEPTS

We consider that a number of concepts introduced in previous sections are useful for the explicit Assumptions of the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework. The order in which we introduce them is not of high importance, all of them are equally relevant and their purpose is to frame our analysis by facilitating questions, which lead to responses and to further questions, in the endless evolutive process of mutual learning, as explained in 2.3 and further developed in Section 3.

2.2.1. Communities

This assumption states that human systems are embodied in communities of people tied together by sharing activities, traditions, practices or goals. Some of them can be more global than local (e.g. the community of performers of classical music) but most evolve in particular places and depend on local contexts. As far as RRI is concerned, there is a tension between R&I conceived at a global level, as something happening in a few places (e.g. Silicon Valley, Shenzhen), and the intrinsically local expression of societal values and needs. Historically the centres of the world-system have produced waves of innovation and modernization to which territorial communities had no option but to adapt, generally in some kind of dependency [Braudel 1979, Wallerstein 2011]. SeeRRI assumes that even if R&I activities are well connected to global trends, their local reception is critical. This is why it makes so much sense analyzing R&I processes with local and regional lenses. In this perspective, regional dimensions and policies are key for the evolution of R&I and hence (potentially) for the success of RRI. This assumption leaves out more abstract and globalized perspectives of R&I and their role. And it also stresses the importance of mobilizing communities around shared agendas and visions. In this perspective R&I processes become a resource and a capacity to achieve territorial visions, and their intertwining with local and regional dynamics and policies adopt a different meaning, as an enabler of autonomous strategies of development.

2.2.2. Transformations

We assume that RRI can become a tool to ignite processes of social transformation in an open and democratic way. The questions leading to RRI originated in Science & Technology Studies (STS) and Science in Society (SiS) programs, and in the context of SwafS the policy later evolved to promote institutional change in R&I organizations through the operational dimensions (Ethics, Gender Equality, Open Access, Public Engagement, Science Education, and Governance). Later on, by considering R&I activities in territorial contexts as whole ecosystems, RRI adopted systemic perspectives. To that end the identification of process dimensions was most useful: Reflexivity, Inclusion, Responsiveness, and Anticipation [Stilgoe 2013] are qualities of responsible processes that take into account interdependencies, a key point (see 2.2.5). Leveraging RRI as a tool for reframing the roles of science, innovation and technology in response to first-order societal challenges is an appealing next step in that evolutionary logic.

Almost a decade after the European Commission adopted the RRI policy, this assumption also responds to the *"six deficits in the global research and innovation system that constitute obstacles for innovations delivering on societal desirable objectives"* [Von Schomberg 2019]. RRI is also meant to be transformational in the sense of promoting in a differential way the success of visionary organizations and ecosystems. This leaves out the possibility that R&I ecosystems could continue "business as usual", with only minor modifications of habits. And it means as well that the learning and

transformational process will have to overcome serious obstacles, and that RRI can also include abandoning certain R&I initiatives, deemed not to be responsible.

2.2.3. Ecosystems

The SwafS-14 topic to which SeeRRI responds explicitly calls for the "*establishment of self-sustaining R&I ecosystems*". This states that R&I activities do not happen out of the blue, as if they were external to society, and are not the product of individual entities, whatever the importance of certain individuals and organizations. R&I ecosystems involve whole chains of actors and processes immersed in society, linked together through nutrient cycles and energy flows, as in biological ecosystems. Moreover, the vitality of R&I ecosystems in territorial contexts requires the participation of all kinds of actors, those directly involved in the production of R&I as well as public administrations, educational institutions, the entrepreneurial class, civil society organizations (CSOs) and citizens at large (Quadruple Helix). This approach broadens the adoption of RRI beyond approaches focused only on changes at the level of individual organizations. It also excludes the concept of R&I as something inevitable, an exogenous factor out of the sphere of societal decisions, and opens the opportunity to its reframing.

According to the characterization developed in WP2 (Active Mapping of SeeRRI Territorial R&I Ecosystems, [see SeeRRI Report D2.1](#)), territorial R&I ecosystems are by definition self-organizing and complex systems acting on a territory, defined as any area characterized by certain geographical features, or sharing cultural, environmental or economic ties. They are driven by innovation activities, co-evolution and interdependencies between different actors, from political, economic and technological scenes. As represented in [figure 4](#), they are never static, and their dynamics are related to society, geography, economy and environment in variable contextual interrelationships, processes, and interactions. They are meant to be suited for radical innovations and niche development.

Figure 4. SeeRRI representation of an R&I ecosystem (source: SeeRRI)

According to the SeeRRI vision, an R&I ecosystem should:

- be complex and self-organizing;
- be flexible to niche development;
- find innovation potential from interfaces and unexpected combinations;
- provide platforms for development and foster peer-to-peer management;
- provide access to global business and civil society ecosystems;
- be open to innovation, co-creation and user engagement (through Quadruple Helix cooperation);
- be trial-based, experimental, and apply rapid prototyping methods in the real world.

2.2.4. Wellbeing(s) in Biosphere

We make the assumption that the aspiration to equitable human wellbeing at peace with the biosphere can be widely shared across people all around the world. For the moment it is just an aspiration. Many scientific capacities already exist to tackle the intertwined challenges of sustainability across disciplines, but the holistic perspective of reconciling human wellbeing with a healthy evolution of the biosphere has not been properly addressed yet. It is beyond the leading edge of R&I, and most R&I activities are not aligned with that purpose. At the same time, in 2020 no definition of “responsibility” can ignore the self-inflicted existential threats that humanity is facing, after Covid-19 showed the systemic fragility of our highly technological civilizations.

Addressing this gap is coherent with the assumption of transformation presented above: a deep formulation of RRI can give it a fundamental role in social transformation. This leaves out more superficial approaches to RRI, and is not just a slightly different way of performing R&I. It goes beyond the “ticking boxes” approach of compliance with a set of static rules. And it provides a framing useful at different scales. At territorial level it can mobilize local communities and groups of stakeholders around the process of elaborating a shared vision, which will be specific to each territory (as detailed in [Section 3](#)). This is why we give a plural tone to wellbeing(s), since the challenges and the responses may be substantially different from one territory to another, depending on the defining contexts and the values, needs and expectations of each territorial community. At the same time, the learnings obtained from concrete territorial contexts will be relevant to debates and policy assessments taking place at national, EU and potentially global levels.

2.2.5. Interdependencies

Human and natural systems are complex. All complex systems exhibit “emergent” behaviours, not reducible to those of their constituting parts. These, be they cells, living beings, organizations or whole ecologies, are autonomous but not independent from each other. System vitality depends on the non-trivial interactions between them. Attention has to be focused on the interdependencies between the constituting parts themselves and with other systems in their environment.

The analysis of complex systems through the lens of interdependencies is a topic at the leading edge of research. More conventional approaches have been focused on splitting the whole into parts and analyzing the characteristics of the parts, an approach sometimes described as “boxes and arrows”. In the approach we propose the focus is on the interdependencies: “arrows” come to the forefront as intense relationships ([see 4.5.2](#)). This approach may look like an invitation to be overwhelmed, compared to more reductionistic options, but it also brings with it opportunities for transformation through mutual learning ([see 2.3](#)). And in its most elaborated perspective RRI is the recognition of interdependencies between R&I processes and four different aspects: the way they are conceptually

framed (reflexivity), society at large (inclusion), the evolution of societal values, needs and expectations (responsiveness), the future consequences of our actions (anticipation). Putting interdependencies at the core of our Conceptual Framework helps formulating questions relevant to more than just individual actors and to understand better the dynamics of evolution of whole R&I ecosystems. It is consistent with this widely used definition of RRI by René von Schomberg:

“RRI is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products.”

Adopting this particular perspective of complexity through interdependencies is also an invitation to consider the multiple contexts conditioning the particular R&I ecosystems under our analysis, since all interactions may be relevant to the behavior of complex systems. This implies that our proposals to promote RRI will necessarily depend on specific characteristics of each particular R&I ecosystem. We expect this to be a differential element favorable to the success of SeeRRI. The project considers three different R&I ecosystems in their territorial contexts (Nordland in Norway, Lower Austria and B30 in Cataluña/Spain) and several more from the Network of Affiliated Territories (NAT) with a less intensive level of analysis. Significant differences between those three territories have been observed, especially in the culture of how public debate and action is conceived. Integrating contextual information in our analysis is vital for the effectiveness of actions to promote RRI. But this statement leaves open the question of how much contextualization is needed and how to practice it.

We need to find a balance between considering all contexts imaginable and designing a practical approach to promote RRI. Many different contexts could be considered, e.g. society, geography, economy, environment, culture, history, politics, and so on. In SeeRRI we decide to use the contextualization best suited to existing frameworks of RRI such as the operational and process dimensions. On one hand, the six operational dimensions of RRI (Public Engagement, Open Access, Science Education, Ethics, Gender Equality and Governance) are used as a framework for the implementation of concrete actions in individual organizations. It has been shown that they are connected to a systemic level of analysis but in an indirect way [Snick 2017]. Addressing changes at the internal level of individual organizations does not necessarily create the optimal pathway to systemic transformations.

On the other hand, the four process dimensions associated to RRI (Reflexivity, Inclusion, Responsiveness and Anticipation [Stilgoe 2013]) fit well with the foundations of our approach. Together they are a good representation of the set of interdependencies on which the evolution of complex R&I ecosystems depends:

- Reflexivity is a requirement to address the dependency between our R&I processes and the way they are conceptually framed, in order to question them and identify what is misleading or missing,
- Inclusion addresses the need to include all types of stakeholders and society at large in all phases of elaboration of R&I processes, starting with agenda and priority setting,
- Responsiveness points to the dependency between R&I processes and societal evolution and challenges, which is insufficiently covered in existing R&I configurations,

- Anticipation is about the dependency between our current R&I processes and their future consequences.

We have then a correspondence between the concept of interdependencies at the core of a complexity-oriented systemic analysis and the four process dimensions considered as requirements for an effective implementation of RRI. This correspondence offers a pathway for our approach to combine the attributes we seek: systemic perspective and practicality of analysis. Thus we adopt it as a fundamental element of the SeeRRI approach, as depicted in [figure 5](#).

Figure 5. RRI-based interdependencies of R&I ecosystems (source: SeeRRI)

In this diagram R&I processes are represented in a central role: this mirrors the expectations of modern societies. R&I are expected to serve societal progress through the advancement of knowledge and multiple (and not necessarily coherent) attempts to provoke deliberate transformations through innovation. As discussed in [4.3](#), present arrangements of R&I processes do not guarantee that they are performed with the responsibility their central role requires. Systemic analysis is needed to go beyond, not as an academic exercise but as a practical way of illuminating aspects generally not considered. This in turn requires looking at R&I processes in different contexts at the same time ([see 4.6.1](#)). [Figure 5](#) reflects the decision of SeeRRI to consider four specific contexts, directly related to the four process dimensions of Responsiveness, Inclusion, Reflexivity and Anticipation. Other relevant contexts such as society, geography, economy and environment are also present in this approach but in an indirect way, since they inform the four ones we use as primary lenses.

2.3. MUTUAL LEARNING: THE ULTIMATE PROCESS OF CHANGE

The purpose of SeeRRI is ambitious: **use RRI to enable the transformation of territorial R&I processes into self-sustaining ecosystems addressing the most pressing challenges of humanity in specific contexts**. This cannot be achieved by using a linear, mechanistic perspective. The temptation is there, though: to get it done, clarify first our final destination and then plan carefully for a succession of steps leading in a straightforward manner to the envisioned goals, while we monitor

the system along the pathway to make sure that it does not deviate too much from the planning. However, there are too many examples in which this kind of planning is ineffective, even in the case of activities which should not escape from the frame: consider big infrastructure projects where everything is carefully planned beforehand but there are too many interdependent factors and then everything results in long delays and budget overruns.

With complex systems the planning method is simply misleading: to start with, the actors in charge of transformation are not external observers, they are themselves part of the system they would like to transform. They cannot adopt an external position from which they could analyze "objectively" the territorial R&I ecosystems of which they are part and transform them through the injunction to adopt certain practices. And the evolution of complex systems is based on endless chains of actions and reactions, questions, answers, more questions and feedback loops with the potential to ruin any deliberate intention, to produce "collateral effects" counteracting the original goals.

This does not mean that it is impossible to achieve purposeful change in a complex system. Complex systems can change and evolve by learning to develop new patterns in order to adapt to a changing environment. Hence, the question about change becomes how to create the appropriate conditions to ignite that learning process. We cannot plan either the modifications of the conditions in order for the system to change exactly in the direction we desire. **The process of creating learning in a complex system is itself a process of learning, and of mutual learning in interaction with the system.** This is a fundamentally different approach compared to the planning strategy. It has to proceed stepwise, be flexible and agile, and take into account the interdependencies and contexts in which the system is evolving as much as possible. There is no way to guarantee that all factors and interdependencies are taken into account. So, there is no perfect recipe for the learning process of making complex systems learn something different from what they are used to. If there was a recipe it would not truly be a learning process. In other words, transformation towards RRI and the SeeRRI project itself are exploratory processes, learning adventures in which we do not know in advance what or how we are going to learn. This is the way that complex systems can change, not by "teaching" them predefined recipes from the outside but rather by creating the appropriate conditions for the actors within the system to start thinking differently and creating pathways towards a shared vision.

It also follows that monitoring the evolution of a complex system cannot proceed with the usual techniques for impact measurement. Decomposing the overall change of behavior into a list of piecemeal indicators may miss the holistic nature of spontaneous reorganization into different patterns. If we recognize complexity in the systems we would like to change, we should not pretend that strategies framed in mechanistic thinking will work. We should rather optimize our strategy for the learning process to succeed. First, by understanding that it is a learning process, not a planning one. Second, by having a wider consideration of the interdependencies and contexts which are relevant to the evolution of the system. As discussed in 4.3 and 4.4 the current framing of R&I ecosystems make them largely blind to the consequences of all their outcomes; moreover, some of these are undesirable or even create existential threats. We also consider that RRI is a good starting point for a more holistic and sensible framing.

Figure 6. Circular process of mutual learning (source: SeeRRI)

Figure 6 proposes a graphical representation of what a circular process of mutual learning could look like, starting each cycle with a reformulation of the general criteria informing every step: at the more general level the criterion is "Wellbeing in Biosphere", but this means different things in different territorial contexts (see 3.3). Then concrete challenges can be identified and responses designed, implemented and checked against the design criteria, and so on, since each cycle is not a step toward a final solution but rather a step upward in the ladder of mutual learning into a different state of the overall system. Communities and the biosphere are represented at the center to express the criticality of their role in the development of territorial pathways towards sustainable wellbeing.

3. INTEGRATION AND USE OF THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1. THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK IN SEERRI

As discussed in 4.1.1, there are good reasons for SeeRRI to develop a new Conceptual Framework. Its purpose is related to the deployment of RRI philosophy and policies and the transformative potential of R&I ecosystems in territorial contexts. To that end a certain way of thinking, derived from the realization and acceptance of complexity, has been adopted. Section 2 describes the work of construction of the Conceptual Framework through the explicit identification of its fundamental assumptions: they are different from those used, consciously or not, in other conceptual frameworks. The exercise of making explicit the assumptions is itself a substantial difference, since this is not often done in the literature on innovation and social transformations. The assumptions selected in our case come partially from the fundamentals of our approach, described in Section 4, and also from the RRI-based contextualization of territorial R&I ecosystems (see 2.2.5). Table 1 shows how the Conceptual Framework and its six fundamental assumptions originate in the intellectual foundations and in the contexts used in our analysis. Assumption Zero is the idea that processes, rather than structures, are central to the description of any kind of system (see 4.2.4).

Foundations	Contexts	Conceptual Framework
Epistemology, cognitive science		Need of a new framework
Process philosophy		Assumption Zero
Analysis of R&I Processes		Ecosystems
Complexity		Interdependencies Mutual Learning
Process Dimensions of RRI		Interdependencies
	Existing frameworks	The whole set of CF assumptions
	Societal evolution & challenges	Wellbeing in Biosphere
	Citizens & stakeholders	Communities
	Future scenarios	Transformation

Table 1. Elements of SeeRRI Conceptual Framework (source: own elaboration)

The assumptions are useful to create common understandings among the partners of the project and as a consequence to give consistency to the activities with the stakeholders in the territories, during and beyond the project itself. The Conceptual Framework is also a generative tool, a process by which a certain number of relevant questions are addressed. This embodies a conception of how complex systems change, through iterative processes of mutual learning under appropriate conditions, an idea

which is useful in any circumstance, within and beyond the project. A more traditional approach could have been based on a linear linking between cause and effect, as depicted in figure 7:

Figure 7. Linear ways of framing (source: own elaboration)

This traditional approach was also an option for SeeRRI: it would have defined an explicit roadmap to go from a certain state A to a desired state B in a number of steps, as well as certain manner of monitoring how progress is made along the pathway. As discussed in 2.4, this is not incorrect in itself but is at least incomplete (and can be misleading). It presupposes that we can observe the systems to be analyzed and transformed from outside (the regional R&I ecosystems) and that we can modify them through the injunction to adopt certain practices. While this may be effective to a certain extent, our theory of change acknowledges that complex systems learn by themselves when exposed to appropriate conditions. Their processes will adapt and make sense of the new context in patterns different from those existing before. They will respond to new questions, and the responses will lead to new questions, and so on, as depicted in figure 8.

Figure 8. Dealing with complex systems (source: own elaboration)

With this perspective in mind, the process of construction and use of the Conceptual Framework is substantially different, it is already part of the process of Mutual Learning of the project (and beyond). As represented in figure 9, it integrates a number of inputs coming from different sources, including

state-of-the-art in systems thinking and innovation (as described in Section 4) but also lessons learned from other RRI projects and relevant findings from other Work Packages in SeeRRI.

Figure 9. Mutual learning starts with the construction of the framework (source: own elaboration)

Figure 10. Circular use of the Conceptual Framework (source: own elaboration)

The use of the Conceptual Framework implements the circular logic of an iterative process, as described in figure 10: it structures a systematic way to ask questions. It can be understood as a question machine providing inputs to the mutual learning process and helping the stakeholders to formulate their challenges in a specific and context-dependent manner which is easier for them to adopt than more general and abstract ones. For those questions to be effective in the development of the relationships with SeeRRI stakeholders, they have to be:

- Easy to understand in stakeholders' specific contexts,
- Relevant to the purpose (aligning R&I processes with RRI in regional contexts),
- Relevant to the intermediate purposes and visions developed by the stakeholders in the project,
- Not trivial, so that the responses can generate new and fruitful perspectives.

The Conceptual Framework does not ensure all this in an automatic way, but it helps the partners to engage in meaningful conversations around relevant questions. For this to happen, the stakeholders do not have to be necessarily aware of all the assumptions and details of construction of the Conceptual Framework. It does not need to be presented to and validated by them, it can actually be kept relatively hidden while producing questions which are useful for the mutual learning process, as described in figure 11.

Figure 11. Involvement of stakeholders in the Mutual Learning Process (source: own elaboration)

The explicit assumptions of the Conceptual Framework facilitate a consistent execution. They are a guiding reference to:

- Orient and align the questions asked and hence the learning acquired with the overall and intermediate purposes of the project;
- Identify not only the questions to ask but also those which are most relevant to the general dynamic of transformation;
- Ensure that relevant aspects are not missed (especially by applying the criteria for self-sustaining processes described in 4.6.5);
- Prevent significant blind spots from blocking the process of learning and transformation.

It follows from this that Work Packages WP3 (Stakeholder Engagement), WP4 (Development & Validation of an Integrated Framework) and WP5 (Implementing Actions) have to work in close coordination, especially as far as the activities with stakeholders are concerned. This implies working together particularly on the questions and activities derived from them. This is ensured by the existence of the WP Task Force as a team working with a common understanding of the goals and activities of the three Work Packages. In practical terms, the WP Task Force works together in defining:

- An agreed set of questions to be addressed with the territorial stakeholders,
- A draft of list of activities to be proposed to the stakeholders and later refined.

Figure 12 presents a graphical interpretation of how the Conceptual Framework works in the overall context of the project and of the interactions between the WPs and with the territorial stakeholders. The label of "SeeRRlization" is just meant to be provocative, for communication purposes.

Figure 12. Overall process within SeeRRI Work Programme (source: own elaboration)

Regarding the implications in terms of goals and outcomes of the three WPs, this elaboration of the Conceptual Framework does not modify substantially what was already defined in the initial SeeRRI Work Programme. The Conceptual Framework accommodates the different inputs from the different WPs as originally planned. It requires a close coordination between WPs and has been enriched by the ongoing conversations with the territorial stakeholders, which is consistent with the approach of mutual learning.

3.2. SET OF QUESTIONS AND ENGAGEMENT PROCESSES

This subsection collects an initial set of questions derived from the construction of the Conceptual Framework and the processes by which the territorial stakeholders have been engaged since the beginning of the project. Formally the engagement has been part of WP3 but WP3, WP4 and WP5 are working in close coordination, in order not only to maintain consistency but also to make the best use of the interactions with the stakeholders, who have the leading roles in the transformation of the territorial R&I ecosystems. Questions are presented here together with the mention of the Conceptual Framework assumptions from which they are derived and in which manner they are being addressed in the project. All questions are formulated as addressed to territorial stakeholders.

*Assumptions
 "Transformation" &
 "Wellbeing in
 Biosphere"*

Question #1: *Can you imagine something like the process depicted in figure 13 happening in your territory, with "Wellbeing in Biosphere" being the main design criterion?*

Figure 13. RRI-based self-sustaining R&I ecosystem (source: own elaboration)

**Assumptions
"Transformation" &
"Wellbeing in
Biosphere"**

Question #2: *What could be the initial formulation of challenge in your territory, which would be meaningful and concrete enough to mobilize a wide community of stakeholders?*

This question has been addressed in WP3. The phrases below summarize the more elaborated responses (see 3.3):

- Niederösterreich: "Decarbonization of the plastics industry",
- Nordland: "Sustainable management of natural resources",
- B-30 (Catalunya): "Zero Waste".

**Assumptions
"Transformation",
"Communities" &
"Mutual Learning"**

Question #3: *In your territory, who should be concretely mobilized around the main challenge and the corresponding vision? How can alliances be built to ensure the challenge is properly addressed?*

Responses to these questions are being elaborated as part of WP3. The identification of relevant stakeholders is complete, as well as their screening according to the PLU criteria (Power+Legitimacy+Urgency). A process for building shared agendas and ensuring engagement of stakeholders is also being developed in WP5.

**Assumptions Zero,
"Transformation",
"Interdependencies"**

Question #4: *How can we convince territorial stakeholders that RRI is in their interest? In particular, how can we convince a business that RRI makes sense as an element of its strategy?*

The first elements to elaborate responses to this question come from the identification of Influencing factors (in WP3, see 3.4), as inputs to the strategic reflections of the territorial stakeholders. Most probably some of the responses will point to factors out of the domain of direct influence of the stakeholders, and can lead to policy recommendations, later on in the project.

*Assumptions Zero,
"Transformation",
"Communities",
"Interdependencies"*

Question #5: *How will the SeeRRI vision impact on important characteristics of existing R&I processes? In particular,*

- *how does a community-centered vision fit with the global connections of existing processes (the "glocalization" factor)?*
- *how does the Open Access orientation of RRI fit with existing arrangements on patents and their exploitation?*

This question is related to two aspects determining the shape of local R&I ecosystems in a global context. In many cases (especially in Niederösterreich), local R&I ecosystems are parts of larger, globally defined networks: their operating mode responds to the demands of a globalized industry (such as plastics) and their direct connection with territorial challenges of Wellbeing in Biosphere is somehow indirect (other than providing high-quality jobs). In this sense, being locally responsible may not be sufficient to make the global process responsible (again, a relevant question for the global plastics sector of which Niederösterreich R&I processes are part). The second aspect of the question is related to Intellectual Property (IP) and its relationship with the Open Access dimension of RRI. In the case of globally-inserted territorial R&I ecosystems, IP is a fundamental factor of the business model of many stakeholders. This question has not been fully addressed yet, it has to be developed in conversations with the territorial stakeholders.

*Assumptions Zero,
"Transformation",
"Interdependencies"*

Question #6: *How will RRI impact the "metabolic flows" of existing R&I processes? By such we mean:*

- *The capture of funding and revenue streams,*
- *The attraction of talent,*
- *The creation and capture of new knowledge.*

Will RRI make a positive difference on these?

The vision and implementation of SeeRRI require creating new processes or modifying existing ones according to RRI principles. This question is fundamental for the analysis of the sustainability of these new / modified processes. This question has not yet been addressed in detail.

*Assumptions Zero,
"Transformation",
"Interdependencies"*

Question #7: *How could it be ensured that RRI processes are more successful than those who do not consider the importance of RRI?*

Together with Questions #4 to #6 above and Question #8 below, this is the heart of the matter (from a complexity perspective based on process philosophy). If conditions are not created to ensure that the kind of processes we would like to see thriving in an R&I ecosystem have an easier pathway to success than those who do not accept RRI, the whole dynamic of the R&I ecosystem will impede the effective deployment of RRI. Some elements of a response can come from the identification of Influencing factors (from WP3, [see 3.4](#)). But systemic factors need to be considered, many of them out of the domain of influence of stakeholders. This will probably lead to policy recommendations at a later stage of the project.

For the moment we have already elaborated a first identification of structural factors that could drive the deployment of RRI in existing R&I ecosystems. At the level of abstraction at which it is defined this identification of factors pretends to be reasonably exhaustive and comprehends perspectives coming from different "theories of change" ([see 4.3.2](#)):

State-driven perspective:

- Regulatory enforcement of RRI
- Changes in public procurement towards RRI-compliant providers

Market-driven perspective:

- New opportunities derived from RRI
- Changes in customers' habits and preferences
- Differentiation through reputational benefit of being RRI-compliant
- Differentiation through quality effects of being RRI-compliant
- Differentiation through cost effects of being RRI-compliant

Co-creation:

- Large scale pro-bono involvement of citizens in RRI activities
- Opportunities difficult to address by non-RRI organizations (e.g. because citizen science is critical)

Cultural change:

- Widespread adoption of a new cultural norm

With this in mind we collected some qualitative evidence. In September 2019 a Questionnaire was submitted to participants in the project as part of WP6 (Impact Assessment and Activities Evaluation). Some of the questions were related to elements of the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework. In particular, respondents were asked to score with "Yes" or "No" the following options, if they considered them or not as factors potentially contributing to the deployment of RRI:

- Top-down institutional pressure (through mandatory requirements, policies, regulations, etc)
- Ecosystem emulation (because relevant actors have been successful by adopting RRI)
- Opening of new opportunities (because RRI brings new opportunities to address, new research topics, new needs for innovative processes and products, etc)
- Competition on quality (because RRI enables differentiation at global level, higher-quality processes or products, etc)
- Competition on costs (because RRI enables more efficiency in processes, use of resources, etc)

- Bottom-up pressure from society (because citizens / consumers are strongly demanding RRI)
- Emergence of new forms of R&I from failures of previous ones (e.g. through radical "citizen science" because "traditional" R&I is not helping in addressing societal challenges, e.g. SDGs)
- New cultural norm (because not adopting RRI has simply become inconceivable)

The Questionnaire was answered by 39 persons from all SeeRRI Consortium partners (for anonymity reasons we are not able to distinguish which answers come from which territory). The results are presented in **figure 14**, which shows the differences between percentages of "Yes" and "No" for each of the mentioned options. Responses are somehow worrying, since only two factors get significant acceptance (more "Yes" than "No") and in both cases only by 28% of difference. So, it seems that only top-down pressure through legal enforcement and regulations, and the existence of new R&I opportunities directly brought by RRI are seen as favourable factors to promote RRI, and even those are not very positive. Competition on quality is also retained, but with only 8% of positive difference. This is in contrast with the strong consensus that cost considerations will not help RRI (negative difference -84%) and that new forms of R&I will not play a relevant role (difference -64%).

Figure 14. Assessment of factors driving the deployment of RRI (source: SeeRRI)

Looking at the same structural issue from a different angle (partially covering Question #6 above), we take for granted that RRI will not be deployed in a systemic way if RRI-compliant processes and organizations do not attract more resources than those not caring for RRI. Resources can be revenues but also volunteer time and other forms of contribution. To analyze this, respondents were asked to score with "Yes" or "No" which of the following factors would be decisive in improving the resource base of organizations committed to RRI:

- Regulatory enforcement of RRI
- Changes in public procurement towards RRI-compliant providers
- Changes in customers' habits and preferences

- Differentiation through reputational benefit of being RRI-compliant
- Differentiation through quality effects of being RRI-compliant
- Differentiation through cost effects of being RRI-compliant
- Large scale pro-bono involvement of citizens in RRI activities
- Development of opportunities difficult to address by non-RRI organizations (e.g. because co-creation is critical)

The results are shown in **figure 15**. Again, substantial scepticism appears on almost all factors, which is somewhat troubling. Only regulation gets a strong backing (+58%). The correct interpretation of both assessments is not easy, but at the very least we could say that respondents do not perceive the conditions for many structural factors to help in the acceleration towards a wide deployment of RRI.

Figure 15. Assessment of factors increasing the resources for RRI organizations (source: SeeRRI)

This issue of which structural factors could or will help to the deployment of RRI has to be further developed in conversations with the territorial stakeholders.

**Assumptions Zero,
"Transformation"**

Question #8: *How do we ensure that RRI processes are self-reinforcing?*

As discussed in 4.2.4 and 4.6.5, as a general criterion for the sustainability of any process it is critical that the outcomes of RRI-enabled R&I processes give a positive feedback (of any kind) to the processes themselves. They should contribute to improve / expand the capacities of the processes (in a similar way as economic benefits expand the capacity of the company producing them). This question has not been addressed yet.

*Assumption
"Interdependencies"*

Question #9: *How do we reflect on future consequences of R&I activities?*

This question is being addressed through the Anticipation Exercises being developed in WP3, which are identifying Future Scenarios, both of desirable and undesirable developments. These can be used as references for developing the reflection.

*Questions coming
from Framework
Assumptions*

The 9 Questions identified above do not exhaust the list of what has to be questioned under SeeRRI Conceptual Framework. The purpose of the initial Set of Questions is not to be exhaustive, it is to ensure that the questions are relevant to the overall purpose of SeeRRI (and of RRI at large), and useful to engage territorial stakeholders into motivating and fruitful conversations. The active inclusion of stakeholders and citizens at large is one of the key aspects of the deployment of RRI and it is by far the most difficult. It is disruptive of existing R&I processes which were not originally conceived for wide consultation and engagement. The degree to which this is achieved depends on at least two dimensions. The first dimension concerns which phases of R&I processes are open to inclusion. A second dimension concerns the audiences to which R&I processes are open. It is natural to involve public administrations and business representatives, but less natural and more difficult to mobilize citizens at large.

Several activities in SeeRRI are intended to address these issues. The mappings produced by WP2 (Active Mapping of SeeRRI Territorial R&I Ecosystems) identify in detail the stakeholders involved in R&I processes in each of the three SeeRRI territories. This was done at two levels: the evaluation of the participation of different sectors, research organizations, educational institutions, businesses, governments and other actors (e.g. consulting companies). The mappings also identify the most relevant actors at the level of concrete organizations participating in R&I processes. This exercise provides valuable information to WP3 (Stakeholder Engagement), which in turn is focused on ensuring that the perspective of SeeRRI is co-created with the stakeholders, among other means by practicing Anticipation Exercises with them.

Regarding the involvement of citizens at large, the question remains open on how to achieve that goal, which may mean many different things, from a basic level of open consultation to stronger involvement through "citizen science" projects or even an actual co-creation with citizens of the agendas for future R&I activities. What is feasible and appropriate in terms of citizen engagement remains dependent on territorial specificities and in particular on the different cultures for public debate and decision-making. In this respect, Austria, Norway and Spain have quite different histories and practices, which are

relevant for the contextualization of this dimension of RRI. Such differences are being revealed in practical terms in the development of the activities of the project itself, especially in WP3 and WP5.

3.3. SHARED AGENDAS AND FORMULATION OF CHALLENGES

Questions #2 and #3 above express the need for an effective manner of engaging territorial stakeholders and for that engagement to have the widest impact on the transformation of territorial R&I ecosystems. To ensure that both needs are properly addressed some kind of guidance is required. This is consistent with the process dimensions of RRI and the systemic analysis developed in previous sections. If evolution is a process of mutual learning rather than the execution of a deliberate plan, one needs to learn how to learn together with the communities involved. This necessitates the development of new approaches since the traditional mechanistic ones will be inadequate. With this in mind, the Generalitat de Catalunya with the support of Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), have elaborated a methodology around the concept of "Shared Agendas". The mobilization of stakeholders is expected to be more effective if they are actors in the creation of shared visions of the future and the present and in the construction of shared agendas of transformation ultimately leading to systemic impact towards the shared vision (see figure 16, [GenCat 2020]).

This approach provides a way to get responses to Questions #2 and #3, and #1 as well. It helps to identify a vision which could be widely shared, initially expressed as a simple slogan without much detail. The slogan can be used to start initiate a learning curve. In the case of B-30 it was done at an early stage of the SeeRRI project: "Zero Waste" was the slogan adopted, a radical vision of circular economy at its best. While it is probably impossible to implement in its entirety this is not critical since the strength and simplicity of the slogan is good enough to open mindsets and mobilize actions.

The concrete manner in which engagement is achieved must be specific to each territory, whether in SeeRRI or beyond. The situations in Austria and Norway are substantially different:

- In Niederösterreich, the focus is on the evolution of an industrial sector, which was deliberately set up with the strategic intention by the public administration to increase the specialization and competitiveness of the region at a global level. Nowadays, the challenge is the dependence of that cluster on some specific industries (e.g. plastics) whose role is being questioned in the light of sustainable development. In this case, engagement is related to the reorientation of an industrial strategy, which has been successful so far, but now faces untypical challenges of low intensity but potentially dramatic consequences (like reputational risks linked to plastics). Maintaining a significant level of high-quality employment is one of the main issues.

- In B-30, the government itself (Generalitat de Catalunya) creates a new context through its intention to give a different meaning to RIS3 policies. By deliberately adopting a systemic and holistic perspective, GenCat is promoting the emergence of a new space for engagement in which there is a community-oriented perspective and a strong emphasis on sustainability and circular economy through the "Zero waste" slogan. This involves the (far from trivial) construction of a new process involving local administrations, the business sector, NGOs and associations, and academic institutions in an unprecedented attempt to explicitly co-create desirable futures.

Figure 16. The development of Shared Agendas in 3 steps (source: GenCat)

- In Nordland, a strong tradition of deliberation and consensus is part of the local culture. Moreover, the entrepreneurial spirit and the balance between wellbeing and the health of the biosphere are well established. Regional planning needs to be agreed between the regional government and the 40 municipalities with legal capacity on land use because legal authority is distributed. The challenge is how to inject new tools and methods into the process of building the next Regional Agenda, to address the sustainable management of marine resources over a large and low-density coastal area, as well as the deployment of wind energy in a practical manner.

In all cases, perceptions obtained from the series of workshops with stakeholders indicate that SeeRRI activities are useful in creating or increasing the degree of engagement. This does not necessarily unfold in a completely straightforward manner, but it happens. In the discussions among stakeholders, these express positive feelings about their involvement in co-creation and in the collective elaboration on territorial challenges.

The way in which each territory describes and formulates the challenges it faces and how these can be addressed by their own R&I ecosystems is fundamental to the purposes of SeeRRI. It is a good synthesis of many different aspects analyzed through all four RRI-based contexts discussed in 2.2.5. Since such formulation did not happen at the very beginning of the project (except to an extent in the case of B-30), this created the opportunity for leveraging knowledge discovery and open discussions before jumping too rapidly to conclusions.

In SeeRRI, the formulation of challenges is an ongoing process through which aspects of the four contexts (Existing Frameworks, Citizens and Stakeholders, Societal Evolution and Challenges, and Future Scenarios, [see 2.2.5](#)) are made visible and influence the questions being asked. Such an evolution at the level of reflection facilitated by SeeRRI is made evident by the adoption of Thematic Foci at the territorial level, two of which did not exist or were not clearly formulated when the project started.

As part of the preparatory work for the SeeRRI Project Meeting with the Territories in Barcelona on 13/2/20, an explicit formulation of challenges was elaborated, which we report here. It includes SeeRRI territories and four additional cases participating in the Network of Affiliated Territories (NAT).

Niederösterreich (SeeRRI partner)

Challenges: The sectorial R&I ecosystem of plastics currently faces several challenges. Plastics contribute a lot to securing the standard of living we are used to today. However, the plastics industry suffers from a very poor image in society and politics, caused by the global discussions on plastic waste. Therefore, several problems are becoming more and more apparent. Among them, there are no longer enough qualified employees and the influx to plastics education is decreasing very strongly. Who would like to start a professional future in a sector threatened with being banned?

The plastics R&I ecosystems develop and produce high-tech products for all aspects of our lives, textiles, food industry, healthcare, household, construction, mobility, energy, infrastructure, etc. Which measures are now required to improve the image and knowledge of plastics in the population in order to establish a correlation with many positive aspects? Considering the RRI approach, how can we develop a strategy in order to obtain the following results?

- Become aware and face the current situation,
- Repair the damage caused by plastics products and waste, by developing specific concepts for this,
- Make attractive a successful plastics industry with high intensity of R&I activities,
- Develop a happy image of the plastics industry that creates many positive feelings, and
- Develop approaches to create attractive jobs with a focus on women.

Thematic Focus: In the future, the plastics industry in Lower Austria will make significant contributions to achieving a **climate-neutral, environment-friendly and resource-saving economy** through its research, developments and products taking into account the entire added value at a global level.

B-30 (Catalunya) (SeeRRI partner)

Challenges:

- To change the current production and consumption model to one based on green and circular economy in order to capture the potential social, economic and environmental benefits of this transformation, benefiting from local resources and articulating effective responses to socio-economic problems in the territory. Within this shared framework, the SeeRRI project focuses on the challenge of promoting the transition of the B-30 industrial territory to circular economy by articulating a shared agenda with the goal of zero waste generation.
- To change mindsets and increase the interaction between quadruple helix players. Research and innovation are linked to complex ecosystems that involve the different players in the quadruple helix (government, academia, companies and civil society), as well as flows of people, ideas and financing that generate multiple interactions. Accordingly, the traditional concept of R&I as a linear process has

been replaced by the idea of dynamic interaction with many different input points and feedback loops and a multidirectional information flow.

Thematic Focus: **Zero waste and circular economy.**

Nordland (SeeRRI partner)

Challenges: In Nordland the coastline and sea play a crucial role in key industries such as seafood, transport, tourism and energy. And the energy sector, including offshore wind and oil extraction, competes for space with the traditional fishing industry. Nordland's coastal communities faced tough long-term challenges such as depopulation, an ageing society, climate change and environmental pollution. In governance perspective, what is the way to balance competing interests in coastal development? What is the approach to find the right balance between creating incentives for industry and protecting the environment?

Thematic Focus: **Responsible coastal management.**

Haifa (Israel) (SeeRRI NAT)

Challenges: Haifa has the worst air quality of all the cities in Israel, leading to high rates of respiratory diseases and cancers. The municipality has set itself the goal of transferring the heavy polluting industries away from the bay and replacing them with clean air employers. There is clear resistance to this from the established interests, unions and port management. The focus is on encouraging a start-up culture, to retain the young talent in the city, and improving the tourism profile with a new international airport and developing other tourist attractions, moorings commerce and housing. The complex nature of this transformation will benefit from the collaboration of all stakeholders to find win-win strategies. It is hoped that the SeeRRI methodology can contribute.

Thematic Focus: **Air quality.**

Montenegro (SeeRRI NAT)

Challenges: After a 30-years-long unsatisfactory transition from socialist planned economy to a capitalist one, Montenegro needs a new wave of industrial development and entrepreneurship based on global opportunities which will at the same time keep the high value of its environment, so important for the people's identity and for overall wellbeing. How to make a completely different investment strategy from what has taken place in the last 30 years and co-create solutions which would change the mindset towards being more entrepreneurial and aware of sustainability issues?

Thematic Focus: Entrepreneurship and business investment to create a **turnaround towards smart specialization and the SDGs.**

Ostrobothnia (Finland) (SeeRRI NAT)

Challenges: The region is well known for its energy technology cluster, part of an industrial sector which is also active in environmental issues, perceived as a business opportunity. But green transformation is a huge concept and requires wider change in society as a whole, as shown in the European Green Deal initiative. So, the main challenge is how to integrate green transformation into existing regional activities.

Thematic Focus: **European Green Deal inclusion in smart specialization activities.**

Serbia (SeeRRI NAT)

Challenges: What is the way forward? How to halt emigration of workers that made Serbia loose more than 5% of its population in the last decade? Is there a policy remedy for brain drain and the decreases of the country's competitiveness, as also happens in other places in Europe? How to make growth inclusive and environmentally sustainable at the same time? And all this while rising inequality, precarity and lack of social mobility are undermining social cohesion with a growing sense of unfairness, perceived loss of identity and dignity, weakening social fabric, eroding trust in institutions, disenchantment with political processes and an erosion of the social contract.

Thematic Focus: **Work force** needed for economic growth and the implementation of smart specialization.

The formulation of challenges is substantially different from one territory to another but in all cases responsibility, in the strong sense of the term, is clearly present and in a way directly connected to the overall challenge of sustainability.

3.4. ANTICIPATION AND TRIGGER PROCESSES

A way of inquiring into the interdependency between the R&I processes we promote in the present and their future consequences is through Proactive Anticipation, i.e. through the deliberate elaboration of Future Scenarios. This is a practical exercise to raise the awareness of stakeholders at territorial level about their collective capacity to co-create their own future (but also to anticipate less desirable ones). Such an exercise is developed in a systematic way by WP3 (Stakeholder Engagement), first through the identification of a wide set of Influencing Factors (see SeeRRI Report D3.1). A STEEPLE approach is used, meaning that relevant factors are scanned across Socio-cultural, Technological, Economic, Ecological, Political, Legal and Ethical dimensions, producing a first list of up to 105 factors. At the moment of writing the present report, the process of identifying Future Scenarios has only been developed with the stakeholders of the B-30 case. It will also be done with Lower Austria and Nordland in the coming months. In all cases, a systematic screening of factors is done in several stages to reduce the whole set to one retaining only the most influential factors in a specific territorial context.

The Thematic Focus of B-30 is "Zero waste", i.e. a vision of radically circular economy. The final selection of Influencing Factors for this case was the following:

- Education and training
- Resistance to change
- Industry in the territory
- Governmental support
- Research and innovation
- Absorbing knowledge and technology
- New technologies
- Business models
- Skilled employees
- Shared agendas

Based on this set, four different Future Scenarios were developed by the participants in a workshop with stakeholders (on 14/2/20 in Barcelona). The scenarios will be documented in detail in SeeRRI Report D3.2, Briefly, they can be summarized as follows:

- Scenario A brings in a more conscious, empowered and inclusive society, with a transversal governance oriented towards territorial challenges and social needs, based on shared agendas and transparent processes.
- Scenario B foresees a technology-enabled bottom-up democracy promoting flexible "degrowth" (a policy promoting the abandonment of GDP growth as main goal of the economy), with connectivity as the foundation for collective intelligence to tackle societal needs.
- Scenario C is "Big Brother 2084", with society under technological control by big corporations, education and research privatized and high levels of inequality, while "Zero waste" is achieved through exhaustive control.
- Scenario D envisions a new creative techno-hippy society, in which education and all resources are focused on promoting creativity in a continuously changing environment, populated by city clusters.

We note the ambivalence present in the development of these Future Scenarios regarding the role of technology and in particular of digitalization. While there is a clear desire for the use of connectivity and digital tools as a means to empower citizens and enable their creativity, they could also be instruments for a more effective control of society by big corporations. The relationship between digitalization and sustainability did not appear clearly in the discussion, or at least not as much as the political dimension of technology-intensive futures. It seems that significant efforts are still needed to question and imagine how further technological development could help in achieving the overall goal of sustainable wellbeing.

It could be argued that thinking about the future does not necessarily make us think differently than in the present. Moreover, it can be shown that many anticipatory exercises are no more than structured extrapolations of current trends and conceptual frameworks as if these were going to persist in the future. This is an obstacle to the opening of our mental space to the true novelties that could emerge. It is also related to the mechanistic worldview questioned in 4.2.1. Hence, much still needs to be developed for a proper exploitation of the tool of Future Scenarios. To that end, complexity-oriented perspectives are not only welcome but required, because they leave room for the unexpected [Poli 2017]. A step in this direction is to use a framing like the one depicted in figure 17 [EEA 2019, Geels 2006], which is consistent with our perspective on emergent properties in complex systems (see 4.5.3 and 4.6.6). Here, social transitions and transformations are not conceived as linear extrapolations but as the outcomes of dynamic processes in which different trends and forces enter into conflict, first to weaken and destroy existing configurations of social processes, then to create new configurations based on emerging innovations. Though, there is no guarantee that those new configurations appear, nor that they unfold smoothly or are necessarily positive in all aspects. The Scenario C "Big Brother 2084" is an example of a viable reconfiguration, which would be judged as negative by many.

Figure 17. Multilevel perspective on social transitions (source: EEA)

In SeeRRI, the exercise of contextualization with Future Scenarios is useful, especially in refining the formulation of territorial challenges. Thinking about the future is also a strong invitation to identify and describe both the desires we have and the visible difficulties to make them real. But are our desires strong enough to initiate the processes triggering the transformations we need? From the perspective of complexity and emergence, as described in 4.6.6, this cannot be guaranteed. SeeRRI posits that RRI can enable transformations of territorial R&I ecosystems towards self-sustaining states in which societal challenges are effectively addressed. The main trigger process for those transformations to happen is beyond the scope of SeeRRI or the capacities of its partners and stakeholders: it is the evolution of humanity at large which is bringing us to the conjunction of many critical challenges at the same time. The pre-condition of being in the vicinity of a critical point is already met, although not universally perceived, and not uniformly expressed in all contexts and places. Then, within the scope of SeeRRI the most important trigger process is to create the space through which territorial communities can deliberately intend to orient the coming bifurcation into a desirable direction. To this general end, a number of sub-processes are already in place:

- The engagement of and conversations with territorial stakeholders,
- The onset of the Mutual Learning Process (see 2.3 and 3.1) and elaboration of the initial Set of Questions (see 3.2) and,

- The creation of Shared Agendas and formulation of challenges (see 3.3).

None of these trigger processes is final. They all lead to further explorations, among other means by identifying concrete actions to be implemented, both at the level of individual institutions and in the context of the territorial R&I ecosystems (this is being done in T4.3 and WP5). As said, no guarantee of success in the transformations envisioned can be delivered at this stage. Though, everything has been put in place to ensure that the steps taken are consistent with the complexity of the challenges.

3.5. BEYOND SEERRI

"Beyond SeeRRI" means different things. For one, it is about the continuation of the processes initiated by SeeRRI in the three territories involved in the project, beyond the date of its termination. Once engaged the stakeholders and created the space for Mutual Learning, there are good chances that those processes will continue because autonomous dynamics are being ignited and they will continue to be fueled by the relevance of the territorial challenges formulated under the general umbrella "Wellbeing(s) in Biosphere": "Decarbonization" in Niederösterreich, "Sustainable management of coastal resources" in Nordland, "Zero waste" in B-30 (Catalunya). The elements making these challenges relevant will not disappear, rather the contrary. Moreover, the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic, though still unclear, may become a reinforcing argument for the vision of "Wellbeing(s) in Biosphere". In any case, for the long-term sustainability of the consequences of SeeRRI in the territories, the elaboration of contextual and lasting answers to Questions #4 to #8 of the Set of Questions (see 3.2) is critical: the success of RRI-enabled R&I ecosystems depends on them. As far as the territorial stakeholders are concerned, those questions will be addressed during the rest of the project. But this reflection also includes a number of aspects beyond what is in the hands of SeeRRI partners and territorial stakeholders: these will be addressed in Policy Recommendations at a later stage of the project.

"Beyond SeeRRI" is also about the applicability of the contents developed in this Report to other contexts in which the same type of purpose is pursued. From this point of view the applicability is indeed very high. The Thesaurus (Section 4) is of universal validity, it contains concepts, knowledge and approaches which can be used in a wide variety of contexts: evolution in the areas of knowledge described is expected, but changes in the epistemological framing of human activities are slow enough to ensure that a shift towards a complexity perspective will mean a significant innovation for years and decades to come. As such, the Thesaurus has the potential for a long period of exploitation.

In turn, SeeRRI Conceptual Framework (Sections 2 and 3) is not a blueprint whose design would have to be dramatically changed in another territorial context where the same intention of SeeRRI would exist. Of course its application depends very much on the details of the three territories involved in the project. But neither the 6+1 fundamental assumptions of the Framework, nor the Set of Questions, nor the spirit inspiring its elaboration are limited to a few particular cases. As a consequence of the complexity approach on which it is based, the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework is by construction resilient: it can absorb well the perturbations derived from its use in contexts different from those for which it was originally conceived.

4. THESAURUS OF CONCEPTS

This is an abridged version of what is developed at length in the [Annex to D4.1](#). The focus here is on a brief explanation of each concept (or area of concepts) and why it is relevant in the context of SeeRRI.

4.1. THE WAY WE THINK

4.1.1. Frameworks

We propose to use the following definition:

*a **conceptual framework** is a set of organized assumptions which frames the analysis on a specific matter and is useful to create knowledge, implement deliberate actions and deliver outcomes in a systematic manner, in particular in the course of a project, or a series of them.*

SeeRRI works at the confluence of two policies of the European Union, namely Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Regional Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialization (RIS3). Both policies have developed their own frameworks and best practices and SeeRRI builds upon them but needs to go beyond because it recognizes that:

- Regional R&I ecosystems of actors are complex systems, they do not fit into linear, mechanistic descriptions of how social processes take place,
- The conjunction of RRI and RIS3 is itself a process of learning and transformation which cannot be effectively planned in a purely linear way.

Consequently, the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework is conceived as a "question machine" based on a state-of-the-art understanding of how complex systems learn and evolve.

4.1.2. Epistemology

Epistemology studies the nature of knowledge and the practices, rules and conditions applying to the process of creation of knowledge. The word is also used to designate each of the different theories of knowledge, not only the discipline as a whole. It is relevant in the context of SeeRRI because responsibility in research and innovation requires making explicit some questions directly related to epistemology. Is the responsibility of knowledge itself a matter of concern? Does the nature of knowledge make it "objective", beyond the reach of human passions and miseries, and then the issue of responsibility affects only the use of knowledge? What makes that knowledge creation can be considered as responsible? [\[Kunneman 2010\]](#). RRI is itself an epistemological endeavour, a reflection on the nature of knowledge and the quality of the process by which knowledge is created.

While SeeRRI is not going to develop its own epistemology, it needs to build upon perspectives of knowledge consistent with the idea that entities and processes of R&I form ecosystems, at different geographic scales. A good point to start elaborating on that need is to address the issue of how knowledge is related to perception.

4.1.3. Perception and Cognition

Our conscious mind does not have a direct access to reality. The access is mediated by our perceptions through multiple channels of communication, most of them unconscious. Our mind makes sense of the flow of perceptions through frameworks of interpretation. These play a fundamental role in the construction of our conscious understanding of reality (what we usually call "knowledge", see figure 18).

Figure 18. Mediations between reality and understanding (source: own elaboration)

At the same time, our mind is not blind to this, so we are able to consciously question how we think about a specific subject. This reflexivity starts by identifying the contours of the frameworks of interpretation we are using, and making explicit what is usually implicit. This is what SeeRRI Conceptual Framework does: elaborate and make explicit its main underlying assumptions. These are statements translating our understanding of the domain in which we work and the ambition of what we pursue. And the relationship between the conscious adoption of a purpose and the framework required for that purpose to be fulfilled has also to be questioned.

4.1.4. Conscious Purpose

According to a frequent way of reasoning, if we want to achieve an explicit goal (e.g. deploying RRI practices across R&I ecosystems), the first step consists in consciously defining that goal in a precise way, then identifying a path of purposeful steps towards the goal and completing our arrangement with a set of indicators meant to measure the degree of achievement of the goal. By doing this we are adopting, consciously or not, a certain framework to formulate what we intend to do in a "problem-solution" mode with a linear perspective: we know where we are and we define where we want to go, it is just a matter of taking the steps forward. It may look natural, but it is based on a certain epistemology, that of "conscious purpose". This implies first that we put ourselves as external observers of the system which we want to change. And second that we have the capacity to perform a number of operations on that system which will make it to change in the desired direction. This is correct in many ordinary actions but may be problematic when we intend to change a complex system, as does RRI.

A case in point is the "War on Cancer", as it was framed at the times of the US Nixon Administration in 1971. The obstacles preventing discovery of a cure for cancer come from its inherent biological complexity [Jupp 2018]. Many of the advancements related to cancer actually came from the investigation of the genome, an example of curiosity-driven research oriented to increase our knowledge of life at large rather than a purpose-driven endeavour oriented to cure specific diseases. Not least, framing a human initiative in war-like metaphors leads to specific actions: declaring an

enemy and defeating it, generally by destructive means. This metaphor is again being used with Covid-19. But maybe by choosing the wrong framework we pursue our goal in the wrong way. All cancer drug therapies have in common that they seek to kill cancer cells and they essentially fail to cure cancer [Huang 2014]. We reason within our consciousness, so we cannot escape from it. But it can make us aware of its own shortcomings. One of them is to ignore the systemic nature of reality whenever we need to achieve an immediate and urgent goal. But when the nature of the goal is itself systemic (as it is in SeeRRI), it seems better to integrate that characteristic in the framework we use. Doing otherwise would make us victims of our blind spots.

4.1.5. Blind Spots

The physiological "blind spot" is the point of entry of the optic nerve on the retina, which by construction is insensitive to light and hence creates an obscuration of the visual field. As a metaphor, we could say that we have blind spots in our observation of the world and of ourselves, which can produce shortcomings in our understanding, especially when they are produced by our unwillingness to see certain aspects of reality. From the point of view of cybernetics (see 4.2.5), human beings as well as societies and ecosystems are self-corrective systems:

"They are self-corrective against disturbance, and if the obvious is not of a kind that they can easily assimilate without internal disturbance, their self-corrective mechanisms work to sidetrack it, to hide it, even to the extent of shutting the eyes if necessary, or shutting off various parts of the process of perception." [Bateson 1968]

Possibly the first blind spot is to think that we do not have blind spots, that our access to reality, even if imperfect and incomplete, is nonetheless objective and continuously improving. This idea could very well prove false. Also, the hypothesis that reality has to be coherent according to what we consciously consider as coherent has been strongly challenged by the developments of physics in the 20th and 21st centuries [Fiorini 2018]. In addition we only give the status of "knowledge" to what we can express through human language while, as Ilya Prigogine said, *"the world is richer than it is possible to express in any single language"*. Our consciousness makes us aware of its shortcomings. The equivalent of the solution to the physiological blind spot is not built into our mental frameworks, it requires attention and the development of a specific kind of thinking, as described in 4.2.

4.2. MODELS OF THOUGHT

4.2.1. Mechanistic Thinking

The paradigm of knowledge of classical mechanics was established at the times of the Scientific Revolution of 17th and 18th centuries and it remained at the core of physics for around a century. The following are its main assumptions:

- Dualism and objectivity;
- Rationalism;
- Separation of scales and contexts;
- Reductionism (see 4.2.2);
- Linearity;

- Static equilibrium;
- Determinism.

The value of these assumptions has been asserted over time by both the theoretical and practical developments derived from them. Success did not materialize only at the theoretical level, such framework has been the foundation for a myriad of practical applications, many of which already existed before the emergence of mechanics as a science (e.g. large buildings, clocks, mills, printers, artillery, and so on) but greatly benefited and expanded in scope, productivity and quality. At the same time the limits of validity of this coherent paradigm of thinking have been explored as well. Physics has since long entered into a dynamic process of creation of new paradigms of knowledge, every time the incumbent one proved to be unable to explain observed phenomena [Fiorini 2018]. Nowadays the universality of the assumptions listed above is questioned by epistemology, based on the inadequacy of using mechanicism to analyze complex phenomena present everywhere. The mechanistic paradigm is still at the center of our frameworks of interpretation, at least in the Western cultures who have largely shaped the globalized humanity we live in. But this does not mean that it is the appropriate framework to deal with challenges of transformation of the kind that SeeRRI envisions.

4.2.2. Reductionism and Holism

Reductionism is the idea that applying techniques of reduction to the object of our analysis increases our effectiveness in the process of understanding that object. One technique is to build simplified models which become the object of our analysis as if they were the reality they represent (as a map represents a territory). Another is to decompose reality into smaller constituents, assuming that the behaviour of the whole can be deduced from the analysis of the parts, while their connections and interdependencies generally play a secondary role. Reductionist thinking and methods have been foundational of many of the areas of modern science. In as sense it is impossible for humans not to be reductionist: we cannot perceive the aspects of reality to which our channels of perception are not sensitive (although we have worked to overcome this with new artifacts such as the microscope and the telescope) and only part of our perceptions get to our conscious mind (although we are consciously aware of this limitation).

The practical effectiveness of explanations obtained through reductionist methods is considered as an argument good enough to validate the methods, and this is usually an invitation to generalize them. But the limitations of the effectiveness of reductionism appear with clarity whenever complexity manifests itself, especially in the form of emergent properties of a whole which are not deducible from the properties of the parts. Most natural and human systems are actually complex (see 4.5.1), they are made of large assemblies of autonomous parts interacting between each other in non trivial ways, and this is also the case of the territorial R&I ecosystems that SeeRRI addresses. For such systems reductionism needs to be complemented by holism, an approach which focuses on the study of complex systems as wholes. The relevance of holistic thinking is growing inasmuch the consequences of our lack of understanding of complexity are becoming more evident. The awareness is now with us that science and technology, as practiced in the last three centuries, can be at the same time an extraordinary factor of progress for humanity and the origin of many negative consequences, some of them potentially leading to self-destruction at a global scale. As a response to this situation, RRI and its questioning of unintended consequences of R&I take a holistic perspective.

4.2.3. Systems Thinking

A system is a coherent set of interdependent parts. It would not exist without the parts nor without the relationships between the parts giving to it an overall coherence. Systems thinking is the most general kind of answer to the limitations of reductionism. The approach builds upon the consideration that reality is systemic, it is a system populated by systems. From the general definition of a system it is difficult to find anything which is not a system, but mechanism deals well with systems which are either simple (a ball, a chair,...) or complicated (a car, a plane,...) but not complex. On the contrary, for the analysis of complex systems mechanism and reductionism are insufficient, or even inappropriate.

Commonalities among systems are important: they have boundaries and internal structures, they depend on their environment and their internal configuration of parts, they exhibit behaviors which can be synergic or emergent (the whole being more than the sum of the parts), and in the case of living beings they can develop intentional actions. Some behaviors are relevant and widespread if one looks at manifestations of life with a systemic lens:

- Persistence;
- Adaptation;
- Homeostasis and resilience;
- Feedback loops;
- Learning and shifting.

4.2.4. Processes and Process Philosophy

Process philosophy considers that reality is the joint outcome of countless processes taking place in parallel over time in specific places and contexts and producing structures in permanent evolution and interaction. Structures are configurations reflecting the state of play of processes at a certain moment. Processes are permanently exchanging energy, resources and information with their environment, created by other processes. There is nothing purely static in them and their persistence depends on their adaptation to context.

Processes are not manifestations of a larger and coherent whole, they are autonomous and engaged in the pursuit of persistence. This also means that they can be in conflict with each other, although collaboration, concatenation and intertwining of processes are much more often observed in nature than competition [Gorissen 2020]. Also, from the conjunction of processes self-organized patterns can emerge (see 4.5.3). And this perspective is aware of the existence of different scales and levels of processes, organized in some kind of hierarchical manner. Processes can have sub-processes and so on, although relations between different levels may not be as simple as implied in the reductionist perspective (see 4.2.2) and the meaning of "hierarchy" may be ambiguous (see 4.6.3). Complexity thinking is to a large extent built upon process philosophy (see 4.5.1).

4.2.5. Cybernetics

The word "cybernetics" was used in ancient Greece to express the governance of people. In modern times it is a discipline dealing with communication and control, and questioning previous conceptions of causality. Linear sequences between cause and effect, and hence a linear conception from purpose to effect, are not necessarily incorrect but at least incomplete. They ignore potential reactions and feedback loops, which is not appropriate when dealing with living beings, and even less if we cannot take the position of an external observer because we are part of the system under analysis. The design of feedback loops to provide stability to engineered systems (see figure 19) has been part of

cybernetics since its inception. But the existence of feedback has wider implications: it outlines the relevance of interactions between parts of a system and the information they carry, and gives a substantial role to communication in conditioning the behavior and stability of systems. By doing that cybernetics opened the door to the conceptualization of complexity (see 4.5.1). And it outlined that all living systems are complex, full of interactions and feedback loops, sometimes extremely intricate. Moreover, it led to the evidence that the relationship with a complex system does not follow the simple cause-effect scheme, it resembles more to an endless cycle of questions and responses.

A Cybernetic Loop

Figure 19. Scheme of a basic feedback loop (source: Wikipedia)

The study of feedback loops acting directly upon a system is now labelled as "first-order cybernetics", while new branches have emerged, as cybernetics of second or higher orders (see 4.6.2).

4.3. INNOVATION AND BEYOND

4.3.1. R&I Processes. Innovation Theory

The current conceptualization of R&I processes derives from the ideas developed after World War II in the USA [Bush 1945] and later replicated by most industrialized countries. It includes a number of ideas still relevant to this day:

- Research and innovation are major expressions of human genius and the foundation for progress of societies, and as such their development should be promoted;
- R&I not only bring better responses to human needs but also protection from a variety of threats and, generate economic growth and prosperity;
- With these arguments in hand, it makes sense for governments to invest massively in R&I;
- The concrete and most effective way to foster R&I is through the existence of different kinds of institutions playing different roles in an arrangement of processes leading from fundamental research to practical applications;

- A requirement for such specialized institutions to be effective is to selectively enroll the most capable people and ensure excellence through competition, collaboration and emulation among the community of scientists and innovators.

The arrangement of R&I processes can be represented as in **figure 20**. Upstream, funding comes mainly from governments, especially due to the strategic role of technology in geopolitical and security terms, but private sources of funding, high-tech industries and the communities of scientists and innovators also play their role in shaping the decisions of R&I agendas. Downstream, the ultimate test of technological innovation is left to the markets. Actually, the pathways from applied research to applications and from these to commercial exploitation are poorly represented by straight lines. Many unexpected things can happen in the intermediate processes and conversely many expected things may not take place. Nevertheless, there is linearity in the deliberate purposes: innovators, start-ups and corporations intend to bring their innovations to commercial exploitation, as the realization that their ideas were appropriate, timely and well implemented. This validation based on market results has evolved in recent decades along with the general trend of financialization of all economic activities.

R&I Ecosystems

Figure 20. Conceptualization of Research & Innovation processes (source: own elaboration)

The expression "R&I ecosystems" outlines the dynamic relationships between the organizations and individuals involved in R&I and how they impact on society. Real processes do not happen in linear ways and complex patterns of interactions are established among a broad set of actors at local, national and international levels. Though, this complexity does not break with the distribution of roles in **figure 20**. Such arrangement has been extremely successful in its expansion and impact in the last 70 years. R&I, as they exist today, are not the outcome of the execution of a well designed plan but the overall success was actually expected to happen out of the systematization and exploitation of scientific inquiry and technological development. Though, that effectiveness produces unexpected and not always positive consequences. These include the possibility of mutually assured annihilation through a vast arsenal of weapons of mass destruction, as well as real threats of self-inflicted

collapse, catastrophes and perhaps human extinction, due to our indiscriminate use of certain technologies to promote material development, such as fossil fuels. Climate warming or the widespread pollution by plastics are just two examples of undesirable effects of R&I, of such size that it is quite strange to label them as "collateral". A shift in our comprehension could come from considering the negative outcomes, as well as the positive, as emergent properties of our complex R&I ecosystems.

Alignment between the extraordinary momentum of technological innovation (especially in areas such as digitalization and AI) and societal challenges (as compiled in the Agenda 2030 [UN 2015]) is not happening spontaneously. That momentum has its own dynamic and autonomy, largely independent from the pressing issues we face [Alvarez-Pereira 2019]. This imbalance justifies deploying RRI policy as a strategic lever to reframe R&I ecosystems away from the possibility of collapse. In order to increase chances of success in this endeavour, SeeRRI proposes to adopt complexity theory to understand better not only the evolution of the R&I ecosystems as they are but especially what kind of additional layers of contextualization and interactions are needed to ensure that the framing of Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) pervades the whole sphere of R&I.

4.3.2. Paradox of Agency. Theories of Change

The concept of agency refers to the capacity of humans to understand reality, make choices and act consciously and purposefully to change aspects of their environment (social or natural). The institutionalization of R&I activities (see 4.3.1) uses this concept in an extreme way: they happen in a small elite of global institutions attracting the most brilliant minds who are clever enough to understand how the world works and change it in a desirable direction. This locates R&I outside of society, bringing the message that "innovation is unstoppable" and that society has to adapt to it, as if it was a natural phenomenon on which we have no influence. This, for the immense majority of people, is actually a denial of their own agency. It is the denial as well of the social nature of R&I processes. Furthermore, we do not consider that the exercise of human agency at the highest level of excellence in scientific knowledge, technological acumen and management techniques can possibly produce negative results as a direct outcome. We label them as "collateral" or "negative externalities", but they happen at scale, as a consequence of our blind spots on the nature of conscious purpose (see 4.1.4 and 4.1.5).

Taking into account the above, how to create the changes in the world that we need to succeed in a holistic transition towards sustainability? We refer here to the four scenarios presented in table 2:

- The "fatalist" scenario is the one in which we live. Human systems are so stuck in their own logic of operation that we are not able to create the required transformations at the appropriate pace (e.g. climate warming or Covid-19);
- The "individualist" scenario ("sustainability through the market") is based on a combination of appropriate regulations and market-driven innovation to do the job. But sustainability concerns are not new [Meadows et al 1972, WCED 1987]. Either we are not using the market tool for sustainability or it does not work well enough, or a combination of both;

<p style="text-align: center;">Fatalist</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>'First, disaster must happen'</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -No governance; wait for events creating windows of opportunity -Actors in stalemate over means and ends 	<p style="text-align: center;">Hierarchist</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>'Let's put a man on the moon!'</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Top-down central management -Government has power or legitimacy; means and ends clear
<p style="text-align: center;">Individualist</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>'Sustainability through the Market'</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Price and tax policy -Legitimacy for such policy; ends known; market can solve all remaining bottlenecks 	<p style="text-align: center;">Egalitarian</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>'A good transition arena will do it'</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Multi-actor Arena process; learning-by-doing action research -Means and ends to be clarified; no dominant actor; actors tend to agree on rough direction of change

Table 2. Modes of transition management [Tukker & Butter 2007]

- The "hierarchist" scenario (with a top-down central management of the transition) seems simply impossible, at least in most countries, China being the obvious exception;
- The "egalitarian" scenario (with multi-actor and learning-by-doing processes) is the one with greater chances of success. However it requires an epistemological shift to understand how complex systems can change. This is the scenario that policies like RRI are promoting, especially when combined with the capacities of communities of actors at territorial levels, as in SeeRRI.

4.3.3. Communities

Communities are important in the context of creating self-sustaining R&I ecosystems based on RRI. Being part of a community is an all-engaging experience with the complexity of life: communities are not organized into ministries and departments as governments and corporations are, they deal with reality as a whole. Think of a family as the smallest example: members have different roles and perspectives but the family is a whole with no purpose other than living together and ensuring the wellbeing of its members. When thinking about what shapes the beliefs and behaviours of individuals, as well as their relationships with their environment, communities are fundamental. Culture plays a central role, in the sense that what communities share and makes them strong is of a cultural nature: they provide meaning. For most communities a defining and all-engaging element is the territory in which they live: geography, language, history, traditions, local knowledge are not separate departments of a territorial community, they are all intertwined in certain ways of living, working, eating, moving, dreaming, loving in a place. Since they are not purpose-driven organizations, it is quite natural for communities to take care, to provide for one another, especially in times when they are stressed for whatever reason. Wellbeing of members is the closest to purpose that a community could have, and it depends on taking care of each other and of the environment from which resources are

obtained. The capacity of communities to organize themselves and take care of scarce resources is a frequent characteristic: commons can be properly and efficiently managed without the intervention of centralized institutions or market actors [Ostrom 1990].

This is relevant when addressing how responsible innovation could work in territorial contexts, at the intersection of RRI and RIS3 policies. Most of communities are located far away from the centers of the globalized R&I ecosystem, and their only option nowadays is to adopt whatever technologies and innovations have been created elsewhere, far from their particular and place-dependent challenges. Within the appropriate conceptual framework, such as the one developed by SeeRRI, territorial communities are able to address, in their own autonomous ways, the challenges of sustainable wellbeing as expressed in their geographical, cultural and historical contexts.

4.3.4. RRI Process Dimensions

We sketch here how the four process dimensions associated to RRI (Reflexivity, Inclusion, Responsiveness and Anticipation [Stilgoe 2013]) are connected to a number of issues outlined in other sections of this report.

Reflexivity is directly related to the frameworks of interpretation conditioning the way we think and translate perceptions into conscious reasoning (see 4.1.2 and 4.1.3). It is a pre-requisite to identify and avoid our blind spots and the pitfalls of conscious purpose (see 4.1.4 and 4.1.5), as well as the foundation of second-order cybernetics (see 4.6.2) and epistemological advances (see 4.2).

Inclusion is related to the role of communities (see 4.3.3) and interdependencies (see 4.5.2) and the need to have a multiplicity of descriptions (see 4.6.1). It gives its full meaning to human agency in the context of R&I, now limited to the small elite of institutions developing R&I activities (see 4.3.2). Also, it opens the door to consider mutual learning as the most effective way for transformation (see 2.3).

Responsiveness is related to the absence or insufficiency in R&I agendas of elements expressing the aspirations of humanity (see 4.4.4 and 4.4.5). It considers many facets for positive transformations (see 4.3.5). And it addresses the limitations of conscious purpose (see 4.1.4) and other approaches to the question of how complex systems can change in a desired direction (see 4.5 and 2.3).

Anticipation is related to the systemic nature of reality (see 4.2.3 and 4.2.5). Anticipation cannot just be an extrapolation of the present, it has to build upon the best of our understanding of complex systems (see 4.5) and capacities for collective deliberation (see 4.6.1) and mutual learning (see 2.3).

4.3.5. Transformations

In the SeeRRI approach R&I are expected to have a transformative role, in the sense of the term "transformation" associated with the UN Agenda 2030 of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [UN 2015]. The SDGs mean no less than a complete overhaul of human civilizations. But reality admits multiple descriptions, and the reflection on our systemic dysfunctions and how to solve them also admits multiple approaches. The challenge may be daunting if we recognize that everything is interdependent on everything else (see 4.2.2, 4.2.3 and 4.5.2). This is why, as manifestations of present challenges become more evident, simplistic answers to complex crises are proliferating. This

is not the path of SeeRRI, the project dares to face complexity because dismissing it is, to the best of our knowledge, a wrong approach.

Transformations have necessarily multiple contexts (technology, economy, governance, culture, society, and so on). The depth of the challenges and hence of the responses to them is such that there is no straight pathway from A to B in ten easy steps. Transformations will be shaped by a complex ecology of ideas and initiatives that are interconnected and not mutually exclusive. The SeeRRI Conceptual Framework does not directly address all the mentioned contexts, but it integrates them through four contexts associated to the RRI process dimensions (see 2.2.5).

4.4. NATURE AND US

The title of this Section wrongly suggests that humans are not part of nature. But this idea of separation is a common blind spot in our relationship with nature, as something different from human-made environment, and also in the dichotomy between nature and culture. From the modern perspective of ecology we realize how much interdependent we are with nature.

4.4.1. Biosphere, Ecology and beyond

In the context of geochemistry four separate components are considered: the geosphere (as the set of all solid parts of the Earth), the hydrosphere (liquid parts), the atmosphere (gaseous parts) and the biosphere as the sum of all living organisms. The term "ecosphere" encompasses biological and physical components of the planet, including the four components mentioned above. The term "ecology" means "the study of our house" and it deals with the interactions among living organisms and their biophysical environment. **In the conception of ecology the idea of evolution is a dramatic change of epistemology.** Leaving behind the consideration of the natural world as static and unchanging, ecology became an effort to understand the dynamic and reciprocal relations between organisms, their adaptations and the environment.

In early 20th century Vladimir Vernadsky widened the concept of biosphere, as ***the global ecological system integrating all living beings and their relationships, including their interaction with the elements of the geosphere, hydrosphere and atmosphere.*** And he defined ***ecology as the science of the biosphere***, necessarily an interdisciplinary endeavour. Vernadsky and others opened the door to an evolutionary perspective of the biosphere as a whole, i.e. as a self-regulating system closed except for the inflows of energy from solar and cosmic radiation and heat sources from the interior of the Earth. The history of the biosphere starts 3,5 billion years ago with processes of "biopoeis" (life created naturally from non-living matter) and "biogenesis" (life created from living matter). Vernadsky also proposed during the 1920s that living organisms could reshape the Earth as surely as any physical force, an anticipatory vision of the modern concept of the Anthropocene [Steffen et al 2007] as a new geological era shaped by humans.

Vernadsky and theologian Pierre Teilhard de Chardin popularized the concept of "noosphere". After the geosphere (inanimate matter) and the biosphere (biological life), the Earth is now in its third stage of development. As the emergence of life fundamentally transformed the geosphere, the emergence of human cognition is fundamentally transforming the biosphere. This systemic perspective integrates the

theory of natural selection, which looks at each individual species, in a wider picture. But the evolution of the noosphere is nowadays threatening its own development.

4.4.2. Ecosystems

The term "ecosystem" designates an assembly of living organisms in conjunction with the non-living components of their environment, interacting as a system and linked together through nutrient cycles and energy flows. The concept is also used in non-biological contexts when systems share some of the following characteristics:

- They are dynamic entities, perpetuously changing and evolving. They are influenced by internal and external factors, and subject to disturbances;
- Their vitality depends on flows of energy and materials (in-, out- and internal flows);
- They are dependent on multiple contextual characteristics;
- They are self-corrective against disturbance through the emergence of feedback loops;
- They are resilient, having the ability to recover from major disturbances.

These features are taken into account in SeeRRI when considering the conditions for R&I ecosystems to sustain by themselves. Without both self-correction and resilience, ecosystems would be unstable and collapse sooner or later. And a manifest characteristic is that diversity contributes to resilience: highly uniform natural or human ecosystems are fragile. Also, causality chains can be complex and take a long time to act. Climate warming is a case in point. Not only feedback loops abound, the chains of events leading from one factor to its ultimate consequences can cover large circles [Bateson 2016]. This represents an epistemological shift: our conceptual framework has to integrate the possibility of long chains of interdependencies producing unexpected consequences of our actions.

On the other hand, collapses of ecosystems are not new in the history of evolution but what is new is the intensity of the impacts of human action on all ecosystems across the planet, of which climate warming and the emergencies it induces are the most spectacular. Hence the study of natural and human ecosystems can no longer be free from the analysis of the human footprints on Earth.

4.4.3. Ecological Footprint

A number of initiatives are raising the awareness on the profound modifications of natural ecosystems due to human activities. The UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystems Services (IPBES) are most relevant, among others. These initiatives are systemic within the boundaries of their topic but do not inquire into the interdependencies between their topic and other dimensions of human activity. In particular, ecological perspectives have been disconnected from social and economic perspectives, which mainly explain why the insufficient political will behind many ecological measures. A more comprehensive assessment of the metabolism of our relationship with the biosphere of which we are part is needed. In the early 1990s Mathis Wackernagel and William Rees defined the concept of **Ecological Footprint** (EF) as a metric measuring how much area of biologically productive land and water an individual, population or activity requires to produce all the resources it consumes and to absorb the waste it generates, using prevailing technology and resource management practices. The EF can be measured in global hectares per person, or in "Number of Earths" required to sustain a specific footprint. Less than 1,7 global hectares per person or, by construction, 1 Earth per person, makes the resource demand globally replicable within the limits of our planet [Wackernagel & Rees 1996]. **Biocapacity** (also measured in global hectares per person) represents the ability of a particular area to produce

biological materials used by humans and to absorb human-produced waste, under current management schemes and extraction technologies. It measures the capacity of ecosystems to regenerate what people demand from them. These indicators of EF and biocapacity do not provide a completely comprehensive representation of the challenges that human societies face, since many relevant aspects are not taken into account. But they are useful in providing an overall outlook and a compelling graphic representation on these issues of critical importance for the future of humanity. As shown in [figure 21](#), at a global level we entered in the 1970s in an increasingly unsustainable regime in which the global Ecological Footprint is higher than the Earth's biocapacity. In other words we are consuming natural resources at a rate higher than the planet is able to produce them (nowadays it is 70% higher), which leads to the destruction of the reserves of natural ecosystems, a very dangerous path downward. This calls for a dramatic reduction in global EF, as discussed in [4.4.5](#).

Figure 21. Worldwide evolution of biocapacity and footprint, 1961-2013 (source: GFN)

These metrics can be used to contextualize the situation of the three territories involved in SeeRRI. Data are not available at territorial level, but the national indicators give useful hints:

- In Austria and Spain, the EF has grown substantially in the last 50 years: from 3,5 to 6 gha/px in Austria and from 2,5 to 6 then down to 4 gha/px in Spain. In the aftermath of the crisis of 2008, Spain reduced its EF by one third in less than 10 years;

- Norway has experienced a decline in its EF from a peak of 11gha/px in the early 1970s down to 5,6 gha/px in 2016. This level is still very high but this shows that substantially reducing the EF is not impossible and does not necessarily entail a collapse in human wellbeing.

- Due to different territorial conditions and population densities, the three countries have very different biocapacities per person: Spain has 1,4 gha/px, Austria 2,9 gha/px and Norway 7,3 gha/px;
- Their national deficit or excess (biocapacity - footprint) is totally different: Norway has a positive balance of 1,7 gha/px, Austria and Spain have negative positions (-3,1 and -2,6 gha/px);
- Differences in evolution over time are significant. In Austria, biocapacity has been initially stable and then slightly declining since the 1990s, while its footprint grew rapidly until 2005 and then stabilized;
- In Norway, biocapacity has been significantly declining, especially since 2005, and its footprint increased from the 60s to the 70s and has been declining most of the time since then;
- In Spain, biocapacity has been stable since the 1960s, while its footprint grew rapidly until around 2008 and then collapsed; it has stabilized and now shows signs of growth once more.

4.4.4. Human Development and its Measurement

Historically the concept of development has been associated to the rapid process of industrialization and urbanization that has characterized the evolution of certain countries in the last two centuries and has now become the benchmark for most of them. After World War II Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and its ratio per capita became the metrics of reference to measure and compare degrees of development in different countries. In the early 1970s the Club of Rome disrupted the global conversation about development by raising the alarms about the unsustainability of any model based on the absence of limits to economic growth [Meadows et al 1972]. That had a huge impact, leading among others to the United Nations coining the concept of "sustainable development" in 1987 [WCED 1987]. More than 30 years later sustainable development is still an oxymoron (see 4.4.5).

Figure 22. The decoupling of GDP and GPI in the USA (1950-2004) (source: Redefining Progress)

Over time, the conventional framing of development has been questioned in many different ways. In the 1980s ecological economist Herman Daly coined the concept of "uneconomic growth" to designate growth which creates decline in quality of life. Marilyn Waring (from the field of feminist economics) promoted the creation of the Genuine Progress Indicator (GPI) to screen out the negative effects of economic growth. Worryingly enough, GPI is stagnant since the 1970s and has completely decoupled from the growth in GDP, at least in the USA (see figure 22).

In 1990 the UN Development Program started elaborating the **Human Development Index** (HDI) [UNDP 1990], integrating health (life expectancy at birth), education (average years of schooling) and prosperity (average income per capita). A level of HDI higher than 0,7 is considered as "high human development". In 2011 the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) launched its Better Life Index, taking into account 11 dimensions reflecting quantitative as well as qualitative aspects of quality of life (housing, education, happiness, work-life balance and so on).

The same year of 2011 the UN General Assembly passed the resolution "Happiness: towards a holistic approach to development", based on the adoption by Bhutan of Gross National Happiness (GNH) a composite index based on four pillars:

- sustainable and equitable socio-economic development,
- environmental conservation,
- preservation and promotion of culture, and
- good governance.

After long work the United Nations launched in 2015, with the unanimous support of the member states, the Agenda 2030 of Sustainable Development [UN 2015], which includes 17 different dimensions or Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs, see figure 23). This has become the official framework for human development. It informs public and private agendas at all scales and gives a political mandate to align all processes of societal evolution with the SDGs. In the light of RRI promoting R&I processes not aligned with the SDGs cannot be considered as "responsible". But using the SDGs as a compass for policy design and governance is a demanding challenge: the framework is composed of 17 goals and 232 indicators, but they do not represent independent dimensions. Reality cannot be splitted into sealed compartments and considering it otherwise leads to a nightmare of entangled trade-offs. Also, a long list of quantitative indicators will always deliver mixed signals: some will be good, others will be bad, on many we will not know what is going on. While macroeconomic governance is focused on the single goal of keeping GDP growth at the highest non-inflationary level and ignores almost anything else, this challenge of "societal navigation" based on the SDGs is one of the obstacles for translating global debates on sustainability into concrete actions in concrete territories. To continue with the metaphor of navigation, we would need a dynamic sense of wind direction and intensity as well as a tentative course to where we want to go, rather than a large and complicated set of interrelated indicators.

Moreover, as discussed in 4.2.1 and 4.2.2, splitting the monitoring of societal evolution into multiple pieces is the kind of mechanistic exercise at odds with real-world complexity. We rather need to engage in a process of mutual learning (see 3.3). This process starts with open deliberation, done with the partners and stakeholders of the SeeRRI project. At the same time, some kind of overall guidance provided by a synthetic compass is welcome. This is not to say that one indicator is by default less mechanistic than many, but if well chosen the compass could be useful for mutual learning. Monitoring is not useless, but it depends on our expectations: if we believe a set of indicators can truly represent the complex patterns present in society, we are probably misled. However, if we use indicators as

alarms leading to uncomfortable questions, that could be useful as a focal point for our inquiry. Our concrete proposal for this synthetic compass is to **consider the state of societal evolution by looking at how much human wellbeing is achieved at what level of ecological footprint.**

Figure 23. The framework of the SDGs [UN 2015]

4.4.5. Wellbeing(s) in Biosphere

In recent years the concept of wellbeing has acquired more prominence in the debates related with the insufficiency or inadequacy of GDP as societal compass. In the context of SeeRRI as a project promoting Responsibility in processes of R&I in territorial contexts, we propose to use the concept of **equitable wellbeing at peace with a healthy biosphere**, in short "wellbeing in biosphere", as the North pole of our compass to navigate the evolution of R&I processes towards Responsibility. We also consider that the pathways towards the realization of that concept cannot be based on universal recipes, they are necessarily dependent on territorial contexts, as developed in the project. This is why the "s" is added in "wellbeing(s)": the same concept can mean different things in different places. To get an overview of the implied challenge we can use a two-dimensional map of Human Development Index (HDI, [see 4.4.4](#)) and Ecological Footprint (EF, [see 4.4.3](#)). [Figure 24](#) shows the distribution of countries with data of 2016. The size of circles is proportional to each country's population. The largest circle represents the world with an HDI of 0,7 (i.e. reaching the threshold of high human development), but an unsustainable footprint of 1,69 Earths. Sustainable Development (SD) corresponds to a quadrangle in the lower right side of the graph where HDI is high (> 0,7) and EF is low enough (< 1 Earth). The area of that quadrangle is getting smaller because its vertical dimension (EF) is measured in terms of global hectares per person and the world's population continues to grow. This graph brings some surprises:

- Sustainable Development (SD) is currently an oxymoron. Countries with high levels of HDI have also high levels of EF: for HDI > 0,9, EF is never lower than 2,8 Earths although it can go up to 5 Earths;
- Many countries with EF < 1 have low levels of HDI. Progress in HDI is accompanied by substantial growth in EF: China rapidly increased its HDI to 0,75, at the expense of having an EF of 2,2 Earths;
- European countries show high levels of HDI at much lower levels of EF than other rich countries (Germany and the USA have similar levels of HDI with very different EFs, 2,97 Earths vs 4,97). But as of today the EF of European countries is still very high;
- As measured by HDI-EF indicators, best performing countries are Philippines, Jamaica, Ecuador, Cuba and Sri Lanka. These are generally not considered as global references;
- No positive correlation exists between R&I intensity and proximity to Sustainable Development.

Figure 24. Human Development Index vs Ecological Footprint (source: GFN)

The venture towards SD faces two challenges that we are not able to meet for now:

- (1) How can we increase low levels of HDI without increasing at the same time the levels of EF?
- (2) How can we decrease high levels of EF without losing established levels of HDI?

Regarding the countries of SeeRRI territories, Austria and Norway have similar positions (HDI > 0,9, EF around 3,5 Earths) while Spain has an HDI close to 0,9 at a level of EF around 2,5 Earths. All of them face the challenge of lowering their footprints while keeping high levels of human development.

4.5. COMPLEXITY THINKING

As H.L. Mencken said, *"for every complex problem there is a solution that is clear, simple and wrong"*. All relevant problems that humanity is facing are complex. They are driven by multiple and interrelated causes, across multiple contexts and interdependencies. Straightforward methods to "solve" complex problems are tempting, but as suggested by Mencken they do not work in real life. What could work, though, is to use an entirely different approach to assess both the problems and our actions.

4.5.1. Complexity and Complex Systems

There are many definitions of complexity, but all of them share the following characteristics:

- Complex systems are **large assemblies of autonomous actors interacting between them and with their environment in non-trivial and especially non-linear ways**. This description is applicable at many different scales, to the assemblies of cells in a body, neurons in a brain, members in a society (human or not), organizations (families, tribes, companies, cities, states, and so on) in a modern human society. It applies as well to ecosystems (see 4.4.2) and to the whole Earth system;
- Not all systems are complex. A car or a plane are examples of very complicated systems, but they are designed not to be complex: we want them to be predictable;
- **All living systems are complex**, whether at individual, group or societal levels. Individuals are themselves large assemblies of lower-scale autonomous actors: they are ecosystems on their own;
- **The overall behavior of complex systems cannot be fully predicted**. The interactions inside and outside a complex system make impossible to precisely compute its trajectory in any modelling space. More generally, radical uncertainty, unexpected behaviors and emergent phenomena are intrinsic manifestations of complexity [Prigogine & Stengers 1997];
- Complex systems are not chaotic, though: they are dynamic, in permanent evolution and open exchange of energy, resources and information with their environment, but their behavior is not erratic;
- **Emergent properties are features of the whole not contained in the parts**. In the vicinity of critical points **creativity** can play a role. Enabled by processes of interactions at high levels of energy exchange, new forms and patterns, self-organization and auto-poiesis may appear (see 4.5.3).
- Analyzing complex systems is **to look at the interactions and interdependencies within the system and with their environment**. Reductionism is not sufficient. Complexity is characterized by the widespread presence of feedback loops, possibly long and intricate [Bateson 2016]. They resemble questions and answers leading to more questions, in an endless process of evolution.

These characteristics of complex systems pose significant challenges to our understanding, especially if we have the deliberate purpose to make a system evolve in a certain direction. Complexity thinking is not the ultimate paradigm of knowledge: as far as we can say, such thing does not exist [Meadows 1999]. It is a perspective telling us that we are actually immersed in an endless process of mutual learning in interaction with the systems of which we are part (starting with the billions of bacteria living

in our body without which we cannot live). Complexity thinking is a tool at hand, only waiting to be developed in its applications, provided that we recognize the limitations of incumbent epistemologies.

4.5.2. Interdependencies

Interdependency is not the opposite of independence. On the contrary, genuine independence cannot be acquired without an awareness of interdependency. Interdependency is the opposite of exclusion. It states that we cannot ignore how much our life depends on our relationships with a myriad of "others". The central concept of complexity thinking is that in a system we should give priority to the interdependencies between the parts of the system and with what lies beyond the system boundaries.

Interdependency is more than connectedness or interactions. Connections can happen at an infrastructure level (as between nodes of telecommunications networks) but do not even suppose autonomous behaviors of the parts. Interactions do not necessarily imply a permanent state of mutual relationship, as interdependency does. So, complexity is not just about parts connected between each other and occasionally interacting, it reflects a dense web of permanent relationships in which mutual exchanges are the norm.

As far as explanations are concerned our scientific traditions are built upon the practices of separating wholes into parts and reducing dimensionality to a few variables of analysis (see 4.2.1 and 4.2.2). Complexity is a shift in perspective: for all the details it could have, representing a system as a collection of "boxes" and a number of "arrows" between them is insufficient. But if everything is related to everything else we face the nightmare of infinitely-dimensional analysis, and we cannot find a way to take into account all interdependencies in our conscious modelling of reality. Though, the shift from neglecting interdependencies to considering them extends the scope and improves the quality of our questions, and it reveals many of our blind spots. This is why the concept is one of the fundamental assumptions of the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework (see 2.2.5).

4.5.3. Patterns, Self-organization and Autopoesis

Patterns of forms are abundant and very diverse in nature: symmetries, trees and fractals, spirals, meanders and vortices, waves, bubbles, tessellations, cracks, stripes (figure 25). Their regularity and beauty have been a matter of wonder since the beginning of time. From the perspective of complexity the existence of natural forms is a manifestation of the concept of emergence, by which something qualitatively new appears out of parts which do not contain it. Forms are the outcomes of processes able to create structures, under certain circumstances (see 4.2.4). They require a constant and open exchange of energy, resources and information with their environment, sometimes leading to the crossing of a threshold through which creativity happens (see 4.6.7).

Self-organization is the key feature for the emergence of patterns, as *"a property of complex systems which enables them to develop or change internal structures spontaneously and adaptively in order to cope with, or manipulate, their environment"* [Cilliers 1998]. That feature makes possible that a system adopts a certain pattern which arises from a different state of the system, either disordered or following another pattern. It happens spontaneously but requires certain conditions, in particular that enough energy is available, but not the control by any external agent. The different states of a system can be represented in a map, where certain areas (called "attractors") signal where the system finds a stable balance and can absorb fluctuations without changing its pattern. But if enough energy is fed into the

fluctuations the system can shift from one attractor to another, one pattern to another. In the vicinity of such critical situations the smallest fluctuation decides unpredictably whether the system goes one way or another, among a set of patterns in which chaos is also an option. And within that framework the role of far-from-equilibrium "dissipating structures" (see 4.6.4) was identified as the theoretical foundation for emergent patterns [Prigogine & Nicolis 1997].

Figure 25. Examples of patterns in nature (source: Wikipedia)

Self-organization is an ubiquitous phenomenon that can be reproduced artificially in simple, non-living systems (e.g. the formation of convection cells in a fluid). It is not the singularity separating non-living things from living beings. But **life, as the complex system par excellence**, has produced a countless number of new and viable forms of living over millions of years.

It is characterized by another feature, "autopoiesis", a synonym of self-creation coined by biologists Humberto Maturana and Francisco Varela. It refers to the unique ability of living systems "to continuously renew themselves and to regulate this process in such a way that the integrity of their structure is maintained. Whereas a machine is geared to the output of a specific product, a biological cell is primarily concerned with renewing itself" [Jantsch 1980]. This characterization of living systems opened new avenues for investigation, related to feedback loops and self-referencing (see 4.6.2 and 4.6.3). Autopoiesis implies that the purpose of life is no other than the persistence of life itself and underlines the capacity of living systems to maintain themselves. They do so by developing new patterns: this is the way they can learn and change, adapting to new conditions [Jantsch 1980]. Such fundamental insights provide hints to promote effective strategies in the transformation of R&I ecosystems (see 2.3 and 4.6). Though, in a form of poetic irony, none of the above actually solves the question of why emergence happens, which may continue to be a mystery inaccessible to our understanding [Morin 2017].

4.5.4. Modelling Complexity

The expression "modelling complexity" is an oxymoron. Models are simplifications of reality meant to be useful for our understanding, while complexity thinking starts from the opposite angle, by stressing how risky it is to apply reductionism and simplification (see 4.2.2). But rejecting the idea of modelling

complexity leads to think that nothing can be consciously understood about any complex system. Many complexity thinkers work beyond the contradiction between modelling and complexity by assuming that *"all models are wrong, some are useful"*, and recognizing that uncertainty is real, not a collateral effect of the insufficiencies of our techniques which could ultimately be eliminated. Then, a fair modelling starts with making explicit the assumptions taken in the construction of the model(s), as SeeRRI does with the foundations of the Conceptual Framework (see Sections 2 and 3). Also, models of complex systems should be open-ended to expand our capacity for perception and engage into processes of mutual learning. With this in mind modelling complexity might be possible if adopting the appropriate epistemology and techniques [Hoffman 2015].

The richness of the field of complexity has given birth to a multiplicity of techniques of description coming from different disciplines of mathematics and natural sciences [Abraham 2002]. Dynamical systems theory, game theory and agent-based modelling (ABM), complex network theory are among the tools being used to build models of complex systems. As discussed in 4.6, the challenges that complexity poses to our conscious mind may be beyond the reach of modelling and even beyond conventional logic. Conversely, interdependencies can be part of a framework of analysis in any discipline, without necessarily leading to a translation into some kind of mathematical modelling.

4.6. AT THE LEADING EDGE

A number of concepts at the leading edge of systems research are briefly introduced here. They have horizontal implications across several disciplines but do not form a consistent theory. Even for those initiated decades ago, their potential is still largely unexploited. They are elements of inspiration for the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework and especially for the ways it can be used (see Section 3).

4.6.1. Contexts and Transcontextual analysis

Analyzing a complex system in only one context is a limitation that we cannot afford. The Covid-19 pandemic shows it in a tragic way: any of its aspects is linked to many others. Health, science, ecology, cities, transport, industry, economy, politics, technology, education, and still others are relevant contexts, all at the same time. Transcontextual analysis takes for granted that this happens with any complex system: it manifests itself across many different contexts, and its persistence, capacity to adapt and resilience (see 4.5.1) are tributary of that multiplicity of contexts. Since all relevant objects of analysis are linked to different contexts, transcontextual research should be the norm, but solid techniques are still needed to offer multiple descriptions of the way an issue is nested in many contexts, and to get across the boundaries between the different contexts. Not least, transcontextual analysis could potentially offer insights for a system shift when this is required, by identifying where reinforcing mechanisms (see 4.6.6) are loose enough.

To date, the most advanced method of inquiry for transcontextual analysis involves the concept of "Warm Data", defined as *"transcontextual information about the interrelationships that integrate a complex system"*, and the process of "Warm Data Labs", especially designed to engage people into conversations on a complex issue from a transcontextual perspective [Bateson & Schutte 2019]. The format is designed to create the conditions for people to grasp complexity by themselves and initiate dialogues leading to a deeper understanding of interdependencies.

4.6.2. Reflexivity and Higher-order Cybernetics

Cybernetics states that in most of issues direct causality does not have enough explanatory power (see 4.2.5). Complex systems are governed by an interweaving of direct and feedback loops, potentially very intricate. On the other hand our conscious mind is aware of its own limitations and this is the foundation for reflexivity, the capacity to reflect on how we think and act, which is embedded in RRI. Second-order cybernetics emerged to inquire on how knowledge is constructed by human observers with their own frameworks of interpretation. Third-order cybernetics has been proposed to address the subjectivity of the observer (second-order) who observes the feedback loops in complex systems (first-order) [Kenny 2009].

Figure 26. Idealized learning process through multiple feedback loops [Sterman 2006]

A practical application is to ensure that models have epistemological consistency for them to be useful in describing complex systems. From this perspective, models are necessarily open to a wide array of possible futures for the system under analysis, and modelling is a process of learning nested in

multiple feedback loops as depicted by the graph in [figure 26](#). As a consequence, learning about complex systems has to be mutual ([see 2.3](#)) [[Sterman 2002 & 2006](#)].

4.6.3. Frontiers of Understanding

Architecture of Complex Systems: Holons and Holarchies

"Holarchy" is an attempt to go beyond the concept of hierarchy, building upon many of the characteristics of complex systems. An holarchy is an assembly of "holons", a word used by Arthur Koestler in 1967 to designate something which is at the same time a whole and a part. For instance, seeds are part of a tree, but a seed contains as well a future tree. Seeds and tree form a holon. The same with the genome and the body. So, it is not only that a part at a certain level can be a whole at a lower one. Hierarchies have by definition higher and lower levels but this is no longer valid in holarchies. The bottom can be a top and the top a bottom. A fractal illustrates this absence (or ambiguity) of hierarchy: at each of its levels the fractal is self-similar, it contains the same patterns. So, holons are at the same time wholes and parts of larger wholes. Individual beings and their societies are holons of intermediate level, in the range of sizes going from the elementary particles to the universe (or the set of multiverses). The concepts of holons and holarchies can be applied not only to biological systems but as well to cultural ones, by considering that the basic units carrying meaning and reproducing themselves as agents of cultural propagation, known as "memes" in the metaphor developed by Richard Dawkins, could be described as holons.

Communication: Double Binds, Schismogenesis

A double bind is the creation of a dilemma when an individual or a group receives contradictory injunctions at different levels of communication [[Bateson 1972](#)]. Responding to one injunction creates a failure in responding to the other, so the response is always wrong. In many situations the dilemma is not easy to confront, so the individual or the group cannot resolve it nor get out of the situation. If double binds are frequent they can lead to emotional distress and eventually mental diseases or learned helplessness, a situation in which an individual or a group perceives a loss of capacity to be in control of its context and to achieve goals. The expression "double bind" has also been used by Norbert Elias in the context of international relations, to designate situations in which two rival states both portray the other as the aggressor and develop highly emotive responses to whatever actions are taken on the other side, leading to dangerous processes of mutual distrust and fear, and potentially of destructive escalation [[Elias 1987](#)].

This is connected to another concept developed by Gregory Bateson, "schismogenesis", as the creation of division between individuals or groups of the same culture. It is the result of cycles of interactions where responses are mutually aggravating, either in a complementary way, one part being aggressive and the other submissive (as happens in social class struggle) or in a symmetrical manner, where both parts are equally aggressive (as in an arms race between rival states). From the perspective of complexity, both double bind and schismogenesis are related to the interdependency between parts, and in both cases emergent phenomena can be outcomes of the cycles of interaction. What emerges is not necessarily positive (mental disease or social conflict), but it could be so if the complexity of the process is understood.

Challenges in Reasoning: Abduction, Logical Types, Impredicativity

Complexity challenges our capacities for reasoning: it generates a perplexity which could be summarized in the saying "**the more we know, the less we know**", because new knowledge also brings new levels of interactions with reality and hence new complexity and unpredictability. This is why thinkers have been experimenting with tools beyond conventional reasoning. One is "abductive logic", which looks for the simplest inference from a set of observations. The process may lead to a logical fallacy (by observing many white swans we cannot conclude that all swans are white), but it can provide useful insights, e.g. starting points for AI algorithms. In practical terms life is full of phenomena defying rationalistic logic, and paradoxes are easily created. To deal with them Bertand Russell proposed a theory of "logical types". It establishes that different logical levels exist: e.g. a class of objects is of a logical type higher than its members and to avoid confusion no class can contain itself as a member. The term "impredicative" was also coined by Russell to designate any object whose definition is self-referential, that cannot be defined without referring to itself.

Life and language are actually full of situations in which circularity leads to confusion, if using ordinary logic. Communication pathologies such as double binds happen because the contradictory injunctions come from domains located at different logical levels. Also, scientific disciplines are built upon the hypothesis that most objects of analysis are predicative: they can be defined by referring to other objects previously defined. But organisms, minds and societies actually produce themselves. Self-organization and auto-poiesis (see 4.5.3) are manifestations of the impredicative nature of reality. More generally the most important things are impredicative: who can explicitly define love or life? If most of relevant things are impredicative, this is no longer an issue. The issue lies in the limitations of our incumbent epistemology in dealing with real-world systems, which are complex and hence impredicative. But this is also a great opportunity to open new avenues for continuing the adventure of knowledge. Complexity is not a further improvement after mechanicism, it is a new beginning.

Levels of Learning

From the perspective of complexity there are different types or levels of learning, corresponding to different levels of abstraction [Tosey et al 2011]. Learning 0 corresponds to the absence of correction of errors and could be qualified as "not learning", but it derives from the learning that stability of behaviour is important. Learning I is about the ability to try different responses within an established set and learn from errors. Higher levels correspond to increasingly higher levels of abstraction in what has to be changed to obtain an appropriate response in a particular situation [Bateson 1972]. In this taxonomy the different levels do not correspond to a hierarchy or a pathway of capacities to be progressively acquired, nor to a segmentation of humans according to their individual capacities to reach one level or another. Learning modes can happen simultaneously and the range of capacities shared by all children is in this respect are much richer than conventional views of education would suggest [Bloom 1992].

What is implied by this perspective of learning at different levels is that dealing with complexity requires enlarging the sets of responses that can be tried (and the sets of sets, and so on) in constant interaction with whatever we are trying to learn about. Hence the idea that mutual learning (see 2.3) is the best (or maybe the only possible) approach for that purpose.

Automated Knowledge Discovery

"Machine learning" is a set of techniques widely used in the domain of "Artificial Intelligence" (AI). Instead of codifying in a machine what are the rules of intelligence, this approach tries to infer the rules from sets of historical data. Progress in AI is fed by combined advancements in algorithmics, the availability of data and capacities to process huge datasets. AI is being publicized by interested parties and the media (not by the scientific community) as a silver bullet to help us address all kinds of challenges. Part of the hype is based on reality, part on extrapolation, along the following scheme:

- Technical achievements make possible to infer patterns from data related to phenomena of interest;
- These patterns are useful for different analyses: description (what happened?), diagnostics (why did it happen?), prediction (what will happen?) and prescription (how to make happen what we want?);
- The reliability of the analyses makes possible the automation of repeatable tasks and the transfer of responsibility on decisions with no or very little human supervision (e.g. in autonomous vehicles).

In a nutshell, this is about the possibility that we build machines whose capacity to process much more information will make them better than us at implementing tasks and taking decisions. The expectations of what AI could do are clearly exceeding what it actually does. This points to the existence of blind spots (see 4.1.5): some are intrinsic to the underlying techniques, others are in the framing of public debates. Since pattern recognition techniques require huge amounts of data from many different cases to be effective, they are necessarily based on decontextualizing information and discarding interdependencies, in other words on denying the uniqueness of each of our lived experiences. Increasing the quantity of data may help to improve our models but it does not change the reductionist nature of modelling, especially if it discards interdependencies.

Also, machine learning provides statistical regularities but rarely a reasoning nor an explanation of why the regularities exist. And since AI predictions and prescriptions are grounded on the extrapolation of identified patterns, their reliability depends on the stability of those patterns and hence we can expect better results when AI is applied to deterministic phenomena (or close to). But life as a whole is non deterministic, and constant interactions between cognitive agents (humans and non-humans) produce new, unexpected and unpredictable patterns (see 4.5.1 to 4.5.3). Complexity is actually increased by the addition of AI-based artifacts as new cognitive agents in new layers of interactions. Hence AI will not help in controlling the world at large: it may be useful for controllability in local contexts and scales but overall it increases complexity and reduces predictability. This is a fundamental limitation as far as the techno-utopia of a world better managed by AI is concerned. But it also opens the possibility of reframing the development of AI for purposes of RRI in the context of our societal challenges.

4.6.4. Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics

Thermodynamics deals with energy and its ability to be used for work. From non-mechanistic perspectives non-equilibrium is the normal state of systems. Putting equilibrium at the core of many scientific disciplines is a blind spot which prevents us from seeing that systems are naturally dynamic, and only static in exceptional situations. Non-equilibrium thermodynamics builds upon this and conciliates physics and biology, the living with the non-living. The total energy of an isolated system remains constant (principle of conservation) while its quality degrades over time (as measured by entropy). Thermodynamic equilibrium is the destination of that process, in which entropy is maximal

and no work can be obtained. For living systems this means death. In other words, living systems are always far-from-equilibrium. This area of study has been extremely fruitful in the explanation of:

- the essential irreversibility of natural and human processes;
- how ordered structures can emerge out of chaos ("dissipative structures");
- the onset of self-organization, when a system shifts by taking one of the branches emerging from the bifurcation in the vicinity of a critical point [Prigogine & Nicolis 1977];
- the role of threshold conditions and entropy production in that process of bifurcation [Jantsch 1980];
- the essential uncertainty which characterizes all complex systems [Prigogine & Stengers 1997];
- the process of "autopoiesis" (see 4.5.4) by which all living systems are able to maintain and reproduce themselves.

In SeeRRI, this branch of physics provides concepts and criteria which can be used by analogy in the reflections on what can make territorial R&I ecosystems self-sustainable through a perspective of RRI.

4.6.5. Criteria for Self-sustaining Processes

Process philosophy is a fundamental element of the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework (see 2.1). Understanding which processes grow and which decline is a central element of analysis of any kind of system. Moreover, to promote a deliberate direction of evolution it is critical to identify the conditions required for the favourable processes to grow and be sustainable over time. In SeeRRI we use the following criteria [Jantsch 1980]:

- Openness: processes have to be able to exchange energy, resources and information with their environment in order to persist, evolve and adapt while keeping their own identity and singularity;
- Energy: processes are not static, they are embodied in far-from-equilibrium dynamic entities, one of whose characteristics is to capture large flows of energy from their environment;
- Auto-catalysis: to keep the processes alive and thriving, their outcomes have to reinforce certain steps of the processes themselves.

In SeeRRI the concept of "energy" is not identical to that used in physics, but human processes also need to capture energy from their environment, and this can be practically assessed: e.g. forms of "social energy" are financial revenues, time and efforts committed by volunteering individuals (not by employees since in that case the net amount of "energy" is supposed to be zero), new talent attracted, attention captured from society at large, and so on. The evolution of human processes and the structures (organizations) to which they give birth can be analyzed in the light provided by the above criteria. If an organization becomes too closed in upon itself or fails in retaining the flow of energy it receives from its environment, it will soon start to decline. The most important criterion is auto-catalysis: it ensures the exponential nature of process growth. An example is the demographic mechanism: the more children are born in a generation, the faster the population will grow. Another example is the appropriation of economic benefits by the company producing them: the more profitable it is, the faster it can grow if the benefits are reinvested in the company operations.

The SeeRRI approach also selects on which processes, at which levels and considered within which contexts it makes sense to focus the actions to promote RRI. A specific selection of contexts is made to make the Conceptual Framework operational (see 2.2.5). As far as the large-scale transformation of R&I ecosystems is concerned, we build from the hypothesis that RRI-based processes have to grow and populate the domain of R&I activities faster than those ignoring RRI.

4.6.6. The Mystery of Life: Emergence from Emergency

"Life is a game whose purpose is to discover the rules, which rules are always changing and always undiscoverable"
 Gregory Bateson (*"Metalogue: About Games and Being Serious"*)

This subsection closes the Thesaurus part of this report (see full version in Annex). Many concepts from the best of systems and complexity thinking have been explored to bring light to the challenge of promoting self-sustaining R&I ecosystems informed by RRI in territories. The ways these concepts are used to build and apply the SeeRRI Conceptual Framework have been described in Sections 2 and 3.

A major conclusion is that **we do not understand reality, we just build frameworks of interpretation through which we try to explain what we perceive of reality**. And this process can be misleading, it produces blind spots (see 4.1.5). But at least we know we have blind spots, and that makes a big difference.

Figure 27. Bifurcations in dynamical systems (source: ResearchGate)

Most probably we will never complete our understanding of the mystery of life [Morin 2017]. But an important fact is that critical points are ubiquitous: all kinds of dynamical systems, especially living ones, go through situations in which they can shift from one state to a completely different one through complex processes of "bifurcation" (see figure 27). To follow the description by Erich Jantsch:

"The essential feature is the internal reinforcement of fluctuations (by autocatalysis) which eventually drives the system over an instability threshold into a new structure. (...) the principle of creative individuality wins over the collective principle in this innovative phase. (...) However, it is not predetermined which structure will come into being. At each level of autopoietic experience, a new version of macroscopic indeterminacy comes into play. The future evolution of such a system cannot be predicted in an absolute way; it resembles a decision tree with truly free decision at each branching point." [Jantsch 1980]

Life has been evolving and innovating during millions of years and taking into account the results, we should humbly recognize that our own capacity to innovate is comparatively limited: nature is able to produce a countless number of viable forms of life by using very few materials and producing no waste. Also, a non-reductionist interpretation of the theory of evolution shows that competition may play have a very limited role, collaboration is more the rule than the contrary [Weizsäcker et al 2018].

As announced by many thinkers, we humans are now at a turning point in the history of civilization: it is time to bifurcate, to **emerge into a substantially different type of organization from the many emergencies in which we are involved**. But emergence does not happen through a smooth and painless transition, it unfolds in critical situations created by painful emergencies during which the outcomes are not predictable nor guaranteed in any way. As repeatedly said, there is no other way to go through the process of emergence than by climbing a steep ladder of mutual learning. But we do not build from scratch. We can use ideas derived from a careful observation of natural intelligence, expressed e.g. as follows, in the form of 10 rules governing how all life works [Gorissen 2020]:

"there is no taking without giving;

it takes an ecosystem to sustain an ecosystem;

interdependency rules; nothing occurs in isolation;

the byproducts generated are as fundamental to evolution as the innovations themselves;

diversity, decentralization, and redundancy build resilience; monocultures and monopolies build brittleness;

keystone species create favorable conditions; conditions that enable regeneration from the bottom-up;

it is the avoidance of competition that drives evolution;

invest in the health of others to ensure your own;

leave it better than you found it;

never take all."

As Leen Gorissen concludes, *"the nature of the future and the future of nature are interdependent"*.

POSTFACE: SYSTEMS THINKING AND RRI IN TIMES OF COVID-19

Writing this Report in Spring 2020 makes impossible to ignore the situation created by the worldwide propagation of virus Covid-19 and its consequences. As with many other activities it has disrupted the execution of SeeRRI itself. Not to the point of putting the project in danger, but the calendar had to be reassessed and all on-site activities had to be either postponed or moved to teleconferencing platforms. Depending on the evolution of the pandemic in coming months it remains to be seen how the planned activities with stakeholders will be carried out. In comparison with many other contexts these are small perturbations, but relevant enough to provoke some thoughts, especially in a project based on the responsibility of research and innovation.

From a systemic perspective the Covid-19 situation raises many considerations and questions, potentially fruitful. We summarize here a number of them.

Systemic fragility. Viruses are tiny and elementary pieces of biological material, among the most primitive tokens of the existence of life on Earth. And still, a particular kind of virus has been able to fully destabilize our globalized and highly technological civilizations. For all the arrogance our knowledge and capacities have given us, there seems to be a huge disproportion between our perception of modernity and our fragility in front of nature. We should learn a lesson in humility.

Interdependencies. The impact of Covid-19 has been what it is not because of the virus itself, but due to the combination of many factors showing how interdependent we are. From a systemic perspective there is nothing new here, reality and in particular life are woven of interdependencies (see 3.2.5 and 4.5.2). But one lesson we could take is that complexity is relevant and feedback loops are everywhere. Without the increased pressure and destruction of natural habitats zoonoses (transfers of viruses from wild animals to humans) would be much less frequent. Without the generalized patterns of mass urbanization in cities with poor air quality, propagation of the virus would have had less impacts. Without globalized infrastructures the worldwide propagation would have been slower (see the moderate impacts in most Asian countries who closed their borders to travels from/to China by end of January). And so on. Interdependencies are extremely relevant.

Framings. As discussed in 4.1 we do not deal directly with reality, we elaborate frameworks to make sense of our perceptions. This is particularly true when facing a pandemic, in which our perceptions are not so useful since we do not see the virus (although we represent it abundantly). The easiest framing is that of the "war on virus", pretty much as we declared the "war on cancer" (see 4.1.4) and many others on issues related to health ("war on drugs" and so on). This military framing is deeply misleading. The virus has no intention of attacking us and we cannot "win" this "war". Viruses were part of the primeval environment from which life emerged on Earth and their number is estimated to be 22 orders of magnitude larger than the number of humans. There is simply no way that we can even fight, not to say win, a war on viruses. The best we could do is to take measures to avoid its propagation, mobilize the resources to deal with the sanitary emergency, and try to understand better the sickness provoked by the presence of the virus (when it happens).

Another common framing about Covid-19 has been to look for culprits, in the form of multiple conspiracy theories (mainly against China) and blaming of incumbent governments. Very rapidly the deadly effects of the pandemic have been associated to a poor "management", and rankings of countries and benchmarkings of leaderships have been produced. While of course decisions taken by

governments have played a significant role, this overestimates the role of human agency and shows that we have difficulties in accepting complex chains of causality. Among others, the state of healthcare capacities of a country and the quality of public health monitoring have been probably more relevant than the concrete decisions taken during the pandemic. But other factors are relevant as well.

Converging factors. At this stage we already know that contagion is not widespread (around 5% of the population in Spain in first weeks of May), but large enough to be sure that it is one order of magnitude higher than the number of declared cases (Spain: seroprevalence around 2 M people, declared cases around 250 k people) and that the overall mortality rate is in the order of magnitude of 1% (again, based on data from Spain, one of the most affected countries). So, it seems obvious that the presence of the virus by itself is not enough to cause major loss of life (unlike other viruses like Ebola, with a much higher mortality rate). Converging factors must be in this case extremely important. Air quality is probably one of them, since it can be the cause of previously high levels of respiratory diseases, especially in urban populations of seniors. Again, this points to complexity.

Unexpected? In recent weeks we have frequently heard that nobody could have imagined the situation in which we are. It was not only imagined but anticipated and actually occurred many times in history. The record of pandemics goes back at the very least to the Plague of Athens in 5th century BCE. Moreover, the pace of new epidemics (mostly coming from zoonosis) has accelerated in the last decades (e.g. HIV/AIDS, avian flu, swine flu, Ebola, SARS, and so on). Alarms were repeatedly raised about the possibility of a pandemic of the kind we have now. SARS got close to becoming one. We simply had a blind spot on this, we preferred not to acknowledge what we already knew.

The role of science. One substantial difference in this pandemic is the role of digital media: it has facilitated the large mobilization and effective cooperation among scientists, as well as a high degree of instant awareness of what is going on and the participation of concerned citizens (including the dark side of it: fake news and so on). High anxiety is naturally focused on the discovery of a vaccine or effective treatments. But when looking at lessons learned from previous epidemics, one of the conclusions is especially disturbing: *"twenty-first century science played a relatively small role in controlling SARS; nineteenth-century techniques continued to prove their value"* [Chew 2007]. This requires further investigation, but it could be that the progress of science in this area is being limited by epistemological barriers.

Responsibility. There are many levels in which responsibility can be considered. A basic one is to avoid the propagation of the virus as much as possible, which for individuals means following the restrictions and recommendations imposed by governments (confinement, social distancing, wearing masks, hygiene). But there are other levels, which have led very quickly to the double bind of "death or economy"? This looks like a "zugzwang" (a situation in chess where all moves are bad). If one reopens activities too fast there will be more contagion and deaths from Covid-19. If too slow the economy will continue to suffer, creating harmful social consequences (including the psychological effects of long confinement). It is difficult to find an optimal trade-off between both injunctions.

Bifurcation. At the beginning of the emergency situation it was quite common to take it as a parenthesis and that we would come back pretty soon to "normality", to "business as usual". But time passed and months later, in the absence of effective treatments we are not yet seeing a return to the prior status quo. It could be that Covid-19 is another manifestation of the critical zone in which human civilizations have entered (see 3.4 and 4.6.6), and that it is not leading us back to where we were but rather to a bifurcation. One emerging scenario is that of an inhuman life, in which we are all converted

into frontline soldiers of the war on virus and other threats. It is a scenario of fear, in which we wear masks and protections to avoid contagion and we keep our distances from others and life at large, in order to keep in "good" health and working to earn a life. Hopefully, other scenarios will slowly emerge.

What is essential? Among other things, confinement could also be taken as an opportunity to reconsider some basic questions, and in particular what makes our life worth living. Responses to that are very personal, and no doubt that confinement has created a lot of frustration for good reasons. But it has also made people rediscover the value of solidarity and caring for one another, as well as the importance of millions of jobs, poorly paid and deemed as "unqualified", without which we simply cannot live. And in a period when consumerism was put to an halt and restrictions were impeding many ordinary activities, the value of creativity was also emphasized. These may be good lessons of the crisis.

Transformative resilience. To conclude with a positive note, there is another branch out of the bifurcation of Covid-19. It is about "*bouncing forward*", creating the opportunity to make the most of our recovery from the hardest part of the emergency. In other words it is about substituting "recovery" by "transformation" towards the kind of societal arrangements that are needed to deal with the many self-inflicted existential threats we face. Covid-19 has shown that we are perfectly able to shift our behaviours instantly if there are good reasons to do it. Now we have to keep that in mind to understand that Covid-19 may have been the revealing factor of our biggest blind spot, that which makes human development incompatible with a healthy biosphere. In an EU context, this means accelerating the deployment of some policies and initiatives which already existed, such as RRI and the European Green Deal, in order to emerge from the crisis through the branch of "*transformative resilience*" [Giovannini et al 2020]. This beautiful and necessary oxymoron shows the way to a society of caring for one another and for nature, a constellation of places where equitable wellbeing at peace with a healthy biosphere is made real.

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